

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
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ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

WORK-LIFE BALANCE
IN GREEK WOMEN
EMPLOYEES
EOX GRO7/3672
SCIENTIFIC REPORT

Co-financed by Greece and the EEA grants 2009-2014

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IASIS NGO

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Work Life Balance: Conclusions

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TEI of Sterea Ellada (HEI),
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1. Introduction

Adults seem to try to find a balance among three different aspects/fields in their life: work, personal and social life. The most challenging task seems to be the effort to find a harmony between work life and family, especially for women, in the current occupational circumstances. More specifically, people, and especially women need to deal with multiple obligations and commitments and their main goal is to find a balance between personal and working life. Employees express the will and the necessity to find practices that may lead to a more balanced life, but also employers seem to understand the cost of a lack of harmony between work and personal life, for their employees. Practices aimed at achieving a balance between life and work can have long-lasting benefits.

Although, work-life balance is a very popular topic in the last decade, it seems that there is no clear definition about this concept. There are many cultural and individual variables that have an effect on work-life phenomenon and define its different aspects (understanding of the concept, causes, consequences, etc.). This concept seems to be sensitive to change according individual needs and priorities, social and financial circumstances, time period and changes in values. However there are some core aspects that function as compass for the work-life programs worldwide: the need for setting and achieving goals and keep a quality of life (low stress, feeling of security and joy) in personal and occupational level. Work-life balance seems to be related with people's need to feel that they have the control of their life, in occupational and personal level, as well as to find those approaches that can ensure a feeling of control.

The main objectives of this research project were the following:

1. Conduct a baseline research, combining qualitative and quantitative methods, in order to examine the rates of work-life balance among Greek women from various employment conditions.
2. Come to a definition what work-life concept means in Greek reality.
3. Examine and suggest the main risk factors for the lack of work-life balance in Greek women, as well as potential protective factors.
4. Examine and describe potential negative consequences of work-life conflict in occupational and personal life.

5. Develop and test a brief intervention/program for Greek women to enhance work-life balance, based on salutogenic model.
6. Develop a questionnaire package for future research, and
7. Increase job satisfaction, quality of life and the balance between work and life.

Consortium expects that this project will enhance the research on Work-Life balance in Greece by providing researchers with a methodology, research tools (structured questionnaire in Greek language, semi-structured interview as well as key questions for the focus groups. Moreover, we will concentrate data from women who work in different employment categories, such as public bodies, private organizations, freelancers, workers, as well as women in different position in hierarchy (higher position, low status), and in various working time conditions (full time or part time). In this framework we will collect and analyze a great number of data which will give us a clear picture on women's perception of 1) what work life balance means for them in Greek reality, 2) what are potential risk and protective factors, 3) what are the consequences in women's quality of life?

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Moreover, Consortium expects that this research will boost and support further research projects and interventions in this field and will help women employees to improve balance between the increased needs in work (due to financial crisis) and the augmented pressure on their personal life (families). This may lead for women employees to improve their productivity and the quality of the working outputs, decrease conflicts in work, as well as decrease job absence and leavings.

Finally, Consortium expects that research results will support policy reforms regarding employment issues for Greek women at workplace.

This research project is designed and was implemented by three (3) partners: IASIS NGO (R& Department), The Technological Educational Institute (TEI) of Sterea Ellada and "Nostos" Organization for social integration.

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In this project, based on previous research projects Consortium decided to examine the work-life balance among women employees, by combining qualitative and quantitative methodology. Data were collected from women employees of different categories of employment covering a wide range of occupations and geographical locations in area of Attica. In the framework of this project, the work-life balance is conceptualized as functioning and satisfaction at work environment and personal life. The key constructs that have been investigated, are work-life balance satisfaction, potential risk factors for work-life imbalance as well as possible protective factors. Moreover, possible consequences of the lack of work-life balance were also examined (quality of life, stress level).

Taking into consideration the bibliography, project's partners have found a great number of factors that are associated with work-life balance phenomenon, such as job satisfaction, life satisfaction, gender egalitarianism, work-family conflict, family to work conflict (Haar et al, 2014), demands of work, culture of work, work orientation, personality characteristics, personal control and coping, age, life and career stage (Guest, 2002).

Consortium used a combination of qualitative and quantitative methodology, enriched with a research intervention on a training curriculum for the work-life improvement. First of all, a literature review was conducted and a research protocol explaining the research design has been developed. Literature review aim was the investigation of various factors associated with the balance between their personal and professional life (work-life balance) of women employees in Greece. Furthermore, 3 Focus groups and 10 interviews, based on the previous studies results, provided us with qualitative data and through descriptive analysis we reduced the factors that we eventually examined in the survey.

In particular, based on the literature review, TEI STEREAS ELLADAS, outlined the process of conducting the qualitative research via focus groups, by utilizing the Nominal Group Technique (NGT) for the investigation of work-life balance of women employees.

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) has been adopted for focus groups analysis, as it was designed to promote effective group participation in the decision-making process.

The Nominal Group Technique was conducted by small groups (e.g. up to 8 participants) in order to reach consensus on the identification of key problems or in the development of solutions. The scope of the focus groups was the elaboration on a systematic methodology to investigate the course of action traced through causes, effects, work recovery activities and external interventions which modify work-life balance. In this way, training needs and solutions facilitating work-life balance will be identified. On the other hand, interviews, aim was to obtain insights into issues pertaining to work-life balance. The interview were audio-taped and the anonymity has been protected.

Via qualitative data Consortium examined the ways participants conceptualize work-life balance, risk factors for lack of work-life balance and potential protective factors. The quantitative data were analyzed in order to examine conceptual frameworks and suggest a model and specific mechanisms that can explain the work-life balance phenomenon. The main aim of the qualitative research was to constrict the variables that the bibliography suggests in order to find the most significant ones for the Greek women employees and move to the next step, the development of the questionnaires package.

For the data collection, trained social scientists conducted the focus groups and the interviews.

After the analysis of the qualitative data, the scientific team developed the scales that were distributed during the survey.

For the survey, the paper- questionnaires have been handed out at workplace by trained people, in order to ensure that the questionnaires will be filled and returned (to ensure a good response rate). The questionnaire package has been developed (and some of the scales have been translated in Greek language) following the psychometric principle. The validity and reliability of the tools have been confirmed.

The survey provided us with a great number of data regarding work-life balance aspects. In parallel the research intervention took place.

Research intervention was conducted in order to examine the role of specific soft skills development, based on a previous piloting European Program, on the work-life balance achievement.

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This training program was based on the salutogenic model, which focuses on the development of the healthy aspects of individuals. The resulting Training Material was the content of the Research Intervention which has been conducted in order to examine the role of specific soft skills development, based on a previous piloting European Program, on the work-life balance achievement. The Training Curriculum was based on the Handbook of the "Balance" project and specific modules have been used to create the training program and material. The training curriculum includes some theoretical presentations and experiential activities (based on non-formal education) aiming at the development of soft skills which seem to relate to work-life balance.

Based on an extended literature review regarding WLB dimensions, its dimensions, its antecedents and its consequences (deliverable of WP2) and based on the training curriculum orientations, a baseline and a follow up measurement instrument of the training intervention was developed. The measurement instrument was designed according to the axes of the training curriculum for the intervention. These three axes were:

- a) Self representation,
- b) Construction of a self-development plan, and
- c) Management of relationships and negotiation skills.

Structured questionnaire was developed to measure the above aspects and thus to evaluate training intervention's outcomes. Baseline and follow up measurement gave us information about the utility of the training curriculum for work-life balance improvement for Greek women employees. We conducted a number of sophisticated statistical analyses, mostly SEM analysis, in order to examine the validity of the suggested model, and to develop our recommendations-skills gaps. In particular, women participated in the intervention program, completed two scales about soft skills level and work life balance (baseline measurement). Women participants, attained the training course/intervention aiming at the soft skills development and one month after the completion of the intervention program, the participants completed the same scales in order for the scientific team to examine any changes in the soft skills level and its association with improved work-life balance reports.

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The main aim, was to examine the role of specific soft skills such as self-awareness, time management, planning and networking on the work-life achievement.

The proposed project addressed the systematic examination of the work-life balance in Greek women employees, causes and potential protective factors, as well as consequences of work-life conflicts.

The main goals of the research project was 1) to offer an in-depth description of the situation as regards work-life phenomenon in female population in Greece, especially under the pressure of the financial crisis, 2) to suggest and test a methodology which can be followed in future studies, 3) to develop some scales and a questionnaire package for future research, 4) to suggest and test a model/conceptual framework, 5) to test a training curriculum and how effective could be to improve work-life balance among women employees, 6) to provide stakeholders with some recommendations for policy reform and plans. The results of the research project may improve our knowledge about the way Greek women understand work-life balance, the needs for a better job satisfaction, work commitment, a balanced work-family relationship, and better life satisfaction.

2. Research Methodology & Findings of Quantitative & Qualitative analysis

Literature Review

2.1. Introduction of literature review

This report has been developed as part of the project titled «Work Life Balance of women employees in Greece (EEA GRO7 / 3672)», which is co-financed by the Financial Mechanism of the European Economic Area (EEA) in the Period 2009 - 2014. This research aims at the investigation of various factors associated with the balance between their personal and professional life (work-life balance) of women employees in Greece.

The initiatives for this research can be grounded upon a series of facts:

1. Organizations with more women in executive positions seem to enjoy significantly higher performance in qualitative and quantitative indices (e.g. Catalyst, 2011), although more recent reports raise doubts about their direct impact on firm's profitability (e.g. Noland, Moran and Kotschwar 2016).
2. If women participate in the economy identically to men by 2025 (full potential scenario), the annual global GDP -compared with a business-as-usual scenario- will increase by 26% (about \$28 trillion or €27 trillion, which is roughly equivalent to the size of the combined US and Chinese economies today). An alternative conservative "best-in-region" scenario, in which all countries achieve the rate of improvement of the best-performing country in their region, would lead to an increase of \$12 trillion in the annual 2025 GDP, equivalent in size to the current GDP of Japan, Germany, and the United Kingdom combined, or twice the likely growth in global GDP contributed by female workers between 2014 and 2025 in a business-as-usual scenario (McKinsey, 2015).
3. Although women are half the world's working-age population, they generate only 37% of GDP, while 75% of the global unpaid work is executed by women, (McKinsey, 2015). Also, it is worth stressing that gender inequality in the workplace is linked with gender inequality in society, (McKinsey, 2015).

4. In Greece, the employment rate for women was 48.9% in 2009 and 41.1% in 2014, the lowest in EU-28, while employment rate for men was 73% in 2009 and 58% in 2014, leading to a gap of almost 18% among the widest in EU28 (Eurostat, 2015).
5. In general, women are underrepresented at every corporate hierarchical level, they have fewer opportunities to advance, and only 30% of women employees in Europe think that the performance evaluation system is not affected by gender (McKinsey & Leanin, 2015). In the same report, work-life balance (WLB) is considered as the most prominent reason for the participants not to pursue a top job.
6. The 2016 Randstad Monitor Survey indicated that 80% of the participants prefer men as their supervisors in Greece, while in 2013 only 52% of employees preferred males in leading positions (Randstad, 2016). In addition, only 60% of the participants believe that women receive equal support regarding their career advancement.
7. Women are stressed by the "double burden" syndrome, which is the combination of work and family responsibilities, as it is found to be the greatest obstacle preventing women from career advancement and success.
8. Regarding the shortage of highly skilled workforce which is expected to reach 40 million workers in 2030, an equal employment rate by women may fill this gap (Ernst & Young, 2011; McKinsey, 2013).

Although the necessity of adopting practices that will lead to a more balanced coverage of personal and professional needs of each employee is evident, at the same time several employers regard that the absence of this balance leads to increased costs while achieving it can bring long-term benefits. However, while employee programs are abundant in some countries, participation is low due to the fact that employees are reluctant to participate for fear of being penalized. For example, more than 90% of both women and men employees

¹ [http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Employment_rates_for_selected_population_groups_2004%E2%80%9314_\(%25\)_YB16.png](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Employment_rates_for_selected_population_groups_2004%E2%80%9314_(%25)_YB16.png)

believe that taking extended family leave will hurt their position at work—and more than half believe it will hurt them a great deal (McKinsey & Leanin, 2015).

While recognizing the importance of achieving WLB for employees is almost universal, the economic crisis faced by Europe, which is harsher in Greece, having started in the 2008 and continuing till today, has resulted in the widening of the gap. Unfortunately, crisis has significantly exacerbated working conditions and quality of life, and work-life balance. Specifically, an increased number of working hours and a consequent reduction in the number of available hours off work, more responsibilities and increased levels of stress resulting out from the fear of job loss have been recorded.

The goal of achieving work-life balance concerns both men and women but is achieved with more difficulty by women due to the double burden they face, which is inherent in our social role model. However, women remain at the center of family life, with all the "traditional" family responsibilities (maternity, child-rearing, household maintenance, organizing family life, care of the elderly, etc). The economic crisis has made the achievement of work-life balance by women even more difficult.

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This report aims to provide the theoretical background for the development of a conceptual framework, which aims to explore WLB by detecting antecedents and consequences of this phenomenon, as well as to formulate a research instrument for the investigation of the underlining relationships among them. The research tools will be designed and modified in alignment with the methodology adopted, that is for both the qualitative (interview, focus group) and the quantitative (structured questionnaires) research.

2.2. Operationalization of Work Life Balance (WLB)

Several business gurus consider Work Life Balance (WLB) as a fictitious concept, they do not recognize its existence, and they acknowledge the responsibility of making work-life choices and living with their consequences. Although, the term WLB is subject to considerable subjective interpretation and socio-cultural variation, it often refers to the achievement of a balance between paid work and life outside work, ranging from childcare and housework to leisure and self-development. Traditionally, WLB was restrained to health, stress-related burnout, work hours, maternity rights, and formal employment, however, demographic and socio-cultural changes have shifted its focus on supporting a better way of life for the employee and to nurture optimal conditions for both the individual and his/her family. In addition, WLB at a psychological level refers to the ability to manage internally individuals' own expectations and external pressure at the workplace (self-esteem, social recognition, motivation, performance culture) and set ambitious but feasible goals, which do not inflict on family or personal obligations. Thus, WLB also encompass flexible working hours, caring responsibilities, the pursuit of intellectual interests (lifelong learning) and other preferences which may be shifted over the career or life stage realized.

Regarding the constructs and measures in the WLB literature, two scales are prevalent and one promising has recently attracted research interest. More specifically, the three core concepts of WLB are the following:

1. *'Work-life balance (WLB)'* defined as harmony or equilibrium between work and life domains (Clarke, Koch & Hill 2004).
2. *'Work-life Conflict'* or *'interference'* perceived as negative or unbalanced outcomes of the competition between paid work and non-work activities. Then, Work-family Conflict has a twofold orientation, referring to work conflict or interference with family, and family conflict or interference with work (Greenhaus & Powell 2006).
3. *'Work-life enrichment'* defined as the extent to which experiences in one role advance the quality of life in the other role (Greenhaus & Powell 2006). Across this line of reasoning, Work-life enrichment attempts to shift the area of enquiry away from tension, conflict and competition, which has traditionally characterized the

relevant WL literature towards positive effects of work-life interplay. In a similar pattern, *Work-life enrichment* may be considered as work enrichment towards family domain, and family enrichment towards work role.

Work-life conflict (WLC) and Work-life enrichment (WLE) have been considered as integral parts of the overall work-life balance literature and several reviews have investigated the antecedents and consequences of these constructs (Kossek & Ozeki 1999; Byron 2005; McNall et al., 2010; Lavassani & Movahedi, 2014). However, it is unclear the extent to which WLB, WLC and WLE are utilized as key constructs in the relevant literature and how these variables are operationalized as outcomes or dependent variables, compared to input or independent variables.

On the other hand, given that work-life balance is a broad and complex phenomenon which lacks a universal definition, it often has been approached by the more narrowly defined and more specifically operationalized construct of work-family balance referring to the “extent to which an individual is equally engaged in -and equally satisfied with- his or her work role and family role” (Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw 2003). Indeed, organizational research exploring the intersection between employees’ work and personal lives has primarily focused on the work and family domains, in particular when referring to women employees, as they traditionally face the “double burden” syndrome (Keeny et al., 2013). This study aims at WLB of women employees playing a focal role in family life, thus the non-work aspect of an individual’s life is referred to the family domain.

Another stream of research integrating and sharing similar aspects with work-family conflict (WFC) and work-family enrichment (WFE) has sparked substantial scholarly interest in the interdependency between the work and family domains (i.e., spillover). Spillover refers to bidirectional effects between work and family (i.e., work-to-family, family-to-work) that generate positive (i.e., experiences from one domain facilitate performance in another domain, such as WFE) or negative (i.e., experiences from one domain inhibit the fulfillment of demands in another domain, such as WFC) interplay between the two roles. Thus, the combination of work-family direction and valence formulates four focal concepts: work-to-family negative spillover (WFNS); work-to-family positive spillover (WFPS); family-to-work

negative spillover (FWNS); and family-to-work positive spillover (FWPS) (e.g. Cho et al., 2013).

2.3. Antecedents and consequences of Work Life Balance (WLB)

Given the centrality of WLB for both personal- and work-life domains, a large body of literature has examined its antecedents (causes) and consequences. The following tables (1) present an exhaustive list of scales developed to measure the various conceptualizations of WLB/WFB:

Table 1. Indicative scales measuring different aspects of WLB/WFB

Reference	Scale/ sub-scale	Items
Milkie and Peltola (1999)	Work-Life Balance	1
Banu and Duraiwandian (2014)	Satisfaction with WLB	6
	Personal Life Interference with Work	12
	Work Interference with Personal Life	14
Rincy and Panchanatham (2010)	Intrusion of personal life into work	10
	Intrusion of work into personal life	18
	Personal life enhancement by work	7
	Work enhancement by personal life	7
Brett and Stroh (2003)	Family to work stress	4
	Work to family stress	5
	Balance	5
Hayman (2005) - Adapted from the Fisher-McAuley et al. (2003)/ Fisher (2001)	Work-Life Balance	15
	work interference with personal life	7
	personal life interference with work	4
	work/personal life enhancement	4
Fisher, Bulger & Smith (2009)	work interference with personal life	6
	personal life interference with work	5
	work enhancement of personal life	2
	personal life enhancement of work	2

Table 1. Indicative scales measuring different aspects of WLB/WFB (cont)

Reference	Scale/ sub-scale	Items
Keeney et al. (2013)	Work interference with life domains Health_Time, Strain Family_Time, Strain Household management_Time, Strain Friendships_Time, Strain Education_Time, Strain Romantic relationships_Time, Strain Community involvement_Time, Strain Leisure activities_Time, Strain	48
Kopelman, Greenhaus & Connolly (1983)	Work conflict	8
	Family conflict	8
	Interrole conflict	8
Clark (2001)	Work/family balance	
	Role conflict (Bohen & Viveros-Long, 1981)	7
	satisfaction with work (Hackman & Oldham, 1975)	7
	employee citizenship (Smith, Organ & Near's 1983 altruism subscale)	6
	satisfaction with home life	4
	family functioning (Fisher & Corcoran 1994 Family cohesion scale)	10
Hill et al. (2004)	Work family balance	8
Cho et al. (2013) Work family spillover (from MIDUS: Midlife Development in the United States)	Work to family negative spillover	4
	Work to family positive spillover	4
	Family to work negative spillover	4
	Family to work positive spillover	4

Table 1. Indicative scales measuring different aspects of WLB/WFB (*cont*)

Reference	Scale/ sub-scale	Items
Carlson, Kacmar & Williams (2000)	Time-based work interference with family	3
	Time-based family interference with work	3
	Strain-based work interference with family	3
	Strain-based family interference with work	3
	Behavior-based work interference with family (Stephens & Sommer, 1996)	3
	Behavior-based family interference with work	3
Frone, Russell & Cooper (1992)	Work-family conflict	2
	Family-work conflict	2
Frone & Yardley (1996); Frone, Yardley & Markel (1997); Gutek, Searle & Klepa (1991)	Work-family conflict	6
	Family-work conflict	6
Wu et al. (2013)	Work-life balance	8
Carlson, Grzywacz, & Zivnuska (2009)	Work-family balance	6
	Work-family conflict	18
	Work-family enrichment	16
Carlson et al. (2006)	Work-family enrichment	9
	Work to family development	3
	Work to family affect items	3
	Work to family capital items	3
	Family to work enrichment	9
	Family to work development	3
	Family to work affect items	3
	Family to work efficiency items	3
Netemeyer, Boles & McMurrrian (1996)	Work-Family Conflict	5
	Family-Work Conflict	5
Eurofound - Third European Quality of Life Questionnaire	Work personal life balance	3
	Work personal life balance options	4

Table 1. Indicative scales measuring different aspects of WLB/WFB (*cont*)

Reference	Scale/ sub-scale	Items
White (1999)	Satisfaction with work-family balance	1
Kezner & Quadagno (2004)	Perceived familyWork-Family Balance	1
Davis, Shevchuk & Strebkov (2014)	Satisfaction with work-life balance	1
Saltzstein, Ting & Saltzstein (2001)	Satisfaction with work-family balance	1
Vanderpool & Way (2013)	Satisfaction with work-family balance	6+1
Valcour (2007)	Satisfaction with work-family balance	5
Hill et al. (2001)	Work-family balance	8
Frone et al. (1992) Frone, Russell & Cooper (1992)	Work-family conflict	4
Rice, Frone & McFarlin (1992)	Work-nonwork conflict	
	Work-family conflict	1
	Work-leisure conflict	1
Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw (2003)	Work-family balance	3
	Time balance	1
	Involvement balance	1
	Satisfaction balance	1

Moreover, an exhaustive list of scales developed to measure potential antecedents and consequences of WLB/WFB available in the relevant literature is presented at the following tables (2 &3).

Table 2. Antecedents of WLB/WFB

Indicative Antecedents of WFB	Indicative references
Career consequences	Anderson, Coffey & Byerly (2002)
Child care support in the workplace (Provision of support policies, Understanding in the workplace, Accessibility of support policies)	Fujimoto, Kotani & Suzuki (2008)
Coping strategies (avoidance-focused/ emotion-focused/ problem-focused)	Rantanen et al. (2011)
Core self-evaluations	Rich, Lepine & Crawford (2010)
Demands	Davis, Shevchuk & Strebkov (2014)
Dispositional factors (optimism, self-efficacy)	Fung, Ahmad & Omar (2012)
Dispositional variables	Allen et al. (2012)
Domain boundary strength	Bulger, Matthews & Hoffman (2007)
Emotional intelligence	Money & Peter (2014)
Employee demands for flexible working practices	Brannen et al. (2000); Coughlan (2000); Den Dulk (2001)
Entrepreneurship	Kirkwood & Tootell (2008)
Family Life Characteristics	Keene & Quadagno (2004)
Family salience	Carlson et al. (2006)
Family structure	Anderson, Coffey & Byerly (2002)
Formal organizational support (care benefits, schedule flexibility)	Anderson, Coffey & Byerly (2002)
Gender role attitude	Li & Sun (2015)
Household chores	Hill (2005)
Individual characteristics (Age, marital status, number of children, number of preschoolers, job title and overtime)	Fujimoto, Kotani & Suzuki (2008)
Individual differences	Makikangas et al. (2013)
Individualism/ Collectivism	Chappell (2012)
Informal organizational support (manager support, career consequences)	Anderson, Coffey & Byerly (2002)
involvement in work and family roles	Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw (2003)
Job control	Beham & Drobnič (2010)

Table 2. Antecedents of WLB/WFB (cont)

Indicative Antecedents of WFB	Indicative references
Job insecurity	Beham & Drobnič (2010); Beham, Drobnič & Präg (2011)
Job salience	Carlson et al. (2006)
LMX	Tummers & Bronkhorst (2014)
Meaningfulness of work	Tummers & Bronkhorst (2014)
Mindfulness	Allen & Paddock (2015)
National culture-risk avoidance	Lucia-Casademunt, García-Cabrera & Cuéllar-Molina (2015)
Negative work-to-home interference	Beham & Drobnič (2010)
Organisational characteristics (hospital) (Number of beds, hospital category, parent body)	Fujimoto, Kotani & Suzuki (2008)
Organizational time expectations	Beham & Drobnič (2010)
National culture-risk avoidance	Lucia-Casademunt et al. 2015
Negative work-to-home interference	Beham & Drobnič. (2010)
Organisational characteristics (hospital) (Number of beds, hospital category, parent body)	Fujimoto, Kotani and Suzuki (2008)
Organizational time expectations	Beham & Drobnič. (2010)
Perceived organizational support (POS); supervisor support; perceived organizational work-family support, also known as family-supportive organizational perceptions (FSOP); and supervisor work-family support.	Kossek et al. (2011)
Personal work/ career goals	Hyvönen et al. (2010)
Personality variables (review)	Makikangas et al.(2013)
Positive thinking and other techniques	Molineux, Fraser & Carr (2013)
Proactive personality	Cunningham & De La Rosa (2008)
Psychological capital	Yardley (2012); Mishra, Bhatnagar & Gupta (2013)
Psychological job demands	Beham & Drobnič (2010); Beham, Drobnič & Präg (2011)
Resources	Davis, Shevchuk & Strebkov (2014)
Role spillover	Keene & Quadagno (2004)

Table 2. Antecedents of WLB/WFB (*cont*)

Indicative Antecedents of WFB	Indicative references
Satisfaction with work-life or work-family policies and programs	Galinsky et al., 1996; Anderson, Coffey & Byrly (2002)
Schedule flexibility	
Sense of coherence	Fourie, Rothmann & Van de Vijver (2008)
Social support at work	Beham & Drobnič (2010)
Time balance	Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw (2003)
Time flexibility in work system (Night shift, Shift work)	Fujimoto, Kotani & Suzuki (2008)
Time pressure	Syrek, Apostel & Antoni (2013)
Transformational leadership	Syrek, Apostel & Antoni (2013)
Work engagement	Siu et al. (2010); Fourie, Rothmann & Van de Vijver (2008)
Work group support	Hill (2005)
Work Life Characteristics - time commitment and job flexibility	Keene & Quadagno (2004)
Work overload	Skinner & Pocock (2008)
Work pressure	Tummers & Bronkhorst (2014)
Work-at-Home	Hill (2005)
Work-family culture	Beham, Drobnič & Präg (2011)
Salary status	Richman et al. (2008)

Table 3. Consequences of WLB/WFB

Indicative Consequences of WFB	Indicative references
Absenteeism	Hughes & Bozionelos (2007)
Attitude toward employer	Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Career satisfaction	Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw (2003)
Employee engagement	Richman et al. (2008)
Expected retention	Richman et al. (2008)
Family satisfaction	Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Innovative work behavior	Mishra, Bhatnagar & Gupta (2013)
Job performance	Hughes & Bozionelos (2007)
Job pressure	Forsyth & Polzer-Debruyne (2007)
Job satisfaction	Saltzstein, Ting and Saltzstein (2001); Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Job stress	Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Life balance	Kopelman, Greenhaus & Connolly (1983)
Life satisfaction	Kopelman, Greenhaus & Connolly (1983); Hill (2005)
Marital quality	Barnett & Gareis (2002)
Marital satisfaction	Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Minimal job effort	Hughes & Bozionelos (2007)
Negative effects on health	Hyman et al. (2003)
Nonwork life satisfaction	Grawitch et al. (2013)
Overall stress	Grzywacz & Carlson (2007)
Performance at the organizational level	Bloom, Kretschmer, & Van Reenen (2006)
Physical well-being	Thomas & Ganster (1995); Frone, Yardley & Markel (1997); Sparks et al. (1997); Martens et al. (1999); Felstead et al. (2002)
Psychological strain	Kalliath, Hughes & Newcombe (2012)
Satisfaction with WLB	Grawitch et al. (2013)
Turnover intentions	Vanderpool & Way (2013)
Well being	Mauno, Kinnunen & Piitulainen (2005)
Work life satisfaction	Grawitch et al. (2013)

3. Core Research design for research instruments

Building on the examination of the antecedents and consequences of WFB recommended in the relevant literature, the following factors were selected as most important and relevant for the Greek context, adopting scales validated by several academics, as indicated in table 4.

Table 4. Selected constructs for the research instruments

Construct	Definition
<i>Work-Family Family-Work Interference/ Conflict</i>	<p>As Carlson, Kacmar & Williams (2000: 250) mention: "... three forms of work-family conflict have been identified in the literature: (a) time-based conflict, (b) strain-based conflict, and (c) behavior-based conflict. Time-based conflict may occur when time devoted to one role makes it difficult to participate in another role, strain-based conflict suggests that strain experienced in one role intrudes into and interferes with participation in another role, and behavior-based conflict occurs when specific behaviors required in one role are incompatible with behavioral expectation in another role... each of these three forms of work-family conflict has two directions: (a) conflict due to work interfering with family (WIF) and (b) conflict due to family interfering with work (FIW)".</p>
<i>Work-Family Family-Work Enrichment</i>	<p>Carlson et al. (2006: 131) also inform us that "...based on current conceptualizations of enrichment (the extent to which experiences in one role improve the quality of life in the other role), or the positive side of the work-family interface, a multi-dimensional measure of work-family enrichment is developed and validated... consists of three dimensions from the work to family direction (development, affect, and capital) and three dimensions from the family to work direction (development, affect, and efficiency)".</p>
<i>Work-Family Family-Work Balance</i>	<p>According to Grzywacz and Carlson (2007: 458): "Work-family balance, defined as the 'accomplishment of role-related expectations that are negotiated and shared between an individual and his/her role-related partners in the work and family domains'".</p> <p>A measure of work-family balance is developed in order to establish discriminant validity between work-family conflict and work-family enrichment (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007; Carlson, Grzywacz, & Zivnuska, 2009).</p>

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
<i>Segmentation Preferences</i>	According to Park, Fritz & Jex (2011: 458) "work-home segmentation preference refer to the degree to which one prefers to separate various aspects of work and home from each other by creating more or less impermeable boundaries around the work and home domains... Boundary theory further posits that one's segmentation preference affects individual work-home boundary management through particular rules and practices". In particular, Kreiner (2006) illustrates, among others, how the interaction between an individual's work-home segmentation preference and the perceived segmentation provided by the workplace affects work-home conflict.
<i>Spouse support</i>	"The amount of instrumental aid, emotional concern, and informational and/or appraisal functions from a spouse" (Michel et al., 2011 cited in Helmlé, Botero & Seibold, 2014: 116; see also Parasuraman, Greenhaus & Granrose, 1992)
<i>Work Life Balance self-efficacy</i>	As Chan et al. (2016: 1758) illustrate "self-efficacy to regulate work and life is defined as the belief one has in one's own ability to achieve a balance between work and non-work responsibilities, and to persist and cope with challenges posed by work and non-work demands".
<i>Supervisor's support</i>	A subscale of the work culture scale (Bailyn, 1997) was used. In this approach three cultural aspects were measured—temporal flexibility, operational flexibility, and supervisors' support for employees' family activities. In particular, Clark (2001) mentions that regarding supervisors' support respondents were asked whether their supervisor understands their family demands, listens when they talk about family, and acknowledges that they have obligations as a family member.
<i>Economic hardship</i>	It was taken under consideration the degree to which the economic crisis has caused the individual's economic hardship. A relevant scale has been developed by Schaubroeck May & Brown (1994).
<i>Coping Strategies</i>	According to Amirkhan (1990: 1073), "in the Coping Strategy Indicator Scale three strategies, although not exhaustive of coping possibilities, do seem to correspond to the most basic of human reactions to threat: a) <i>Problem Solving</i> , a strategy of direct assault, seems derivative of primitive "fight" tendencies, b) <i>Avoidance</i> , a panoply of escape responses, seems to derive from ancient "flight" inclinations, c) The strategy of <i>Seeking Support</i> seems to tap a primal need for human contact in times of duress, for reasons beyond whatever material aid, advice, or distraction that contact might provide".
<i>Work recovery</i>	"Recovery refers to processes opposite to such strain processes and

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
<i>experiences</i>	becomes evident in the reduction or elimination of strain reactions... recovery experiences to characterize attributes associated with off-job activities contributing to recovery" (Sonnentag, Binnewies & Mojza 2008: 675). Work recovery activities have been found to have an important effect on work life balance (e.g. Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007; Trougakos et al., 2008; Cropley et al., 2012).
<i>Workplace anxiety</i>	"Workplace anxiety is subsumed under the broader construct of performance anxiety, which reflects feelings of apprehension about the execution of specific tasks... Workplace anxiety is conceptually and empirically related to other types of anxiety and related affective constructs, but is not redundant with these constructs. It is distinct from state-based anxiety because in contrast to a transient situation-specific trait, it reflects general feelings of work-related anxiety that manifest over time" (McCarthy, Trougakos, & Cheng, 2015: 2).
<i>Work stress</i>	Work stress is another important aspect in the WLB literature. "...The subjective evaluation of the level of experienced stress associated with specific stressors" (Cavanaugh et al., 2000: 65), namely "challenge stressors were defined as work-related demands or circumstances that, although potentially stressful, have associated potential gains for individuals; hindrance stressors were defined as work-related demands or circumstances that tend to constrain or interfere with an individual's work achievement and that do not tend to be associated with potential gains for the individual." (see e.g. Caplan et al., 1975; Ivancevich & Matteson, 1983; Sandman, 1992; Cavanaugh et al., 2000).
<i>Emotional exhaustion</i>	According to Maslach and Jackson (1981), a basic feature of the burnout syndrome is increased feelings of emotional exhaustion. Emotional exhaustion is a subscale in the Maslach Burnout Inventory. In this subscale feelings of being emotionally overextended and exhausted by one's work are been measured.
<i>Work-nonwork boundary strength</i>	Hecht and Allen (2009: 840) illustrate that "the boundaries that exist between individuals' work and their (personal) lives outside of work... demarcates what belongs to each domain and establishes their distinctiveness... Boundary strength is most closely associated with the segmentation-integration model, which holds that there is a continuum reflecting the extent to which work and nonwork can be kept separate from, or intermingled with, one another... Work-nonwork boundary is bi-directional, the extent to which work and nonwork permeate each other depends on whether one is talking about spillover of work to nonwork or vice versa".
<i>Procrastination</i>	According to Lay (1986), procrastination is described as the tendency

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
	to postpone something that is necessary to be done in order to attain a goal.
<i>Time management</i>	According to Mudrack (1997), time structuring and management is conceived based on a 5 factor model: a) time management mechanics, b) setting goals and priorities in the short term, c) perceived control of time, d) preference for organization, e) setting goals and priorities in the long-term (for more information about Time Management Behavior Scale see Macan et al., 1990).
<i>Relationship between personal/family life & work life in the present and what it is considered as ideal relationship between these two life spheres</i>	The relationship between personal/family life & work life is represented as a continuum. In one side there is the personal/family life and in the other the work life. Everyone is thought to be able to illustrate to which end of this continuum she/he feels closer at the present or what she/he considers as an ideal relationship between personal/family life & work life in general. On this basis it was developed a quick and easy way to measure this relationship.
<i>Distribution of hours spent on a typical day</i>	Distribution of time spent among work, household/family duties, personal life, spare time and sleep can serve as a direct measurement of the relationship between different spheres of life. A measurement like this can help us to overcome limitations of self-reporting judgments. (see e.g. Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw, 2003; Hill et al., 2004; Hill, 2005).
<i>Optimism, anxiety, exhaustion, time offer and commitment, self-efficacy in personal/family life and work life</i>	These variables have been found to affect the relationship between work and life (see e.g. Frone, Russell & Cooper, 1992; Allen, 2001; Wayne et al., 2007). The measurement of these variables was designed based on research objectives. The basic concept was that each construct can be represented in a continuum with two extreme ends (positive and negative estimation), and everyone is thought to be able to illustrate with a quick and easy way to which end of this continuum she/he feels closer.
<i>Quality of life (World Health Organisation quality of life-Abbreviated Version WHOQOL-BREF)</i>	"Individuals' perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations, standards and concerns" (World Health Organization, 1996:5).

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
<i>Values</i>	According to Schwartz's theory (1992), "values are desirable goals that serve as guiding principles in people's lives. They are socially approved verbal representations of basic motivations... A set of ten motivationally distinct types of values was proposed (common to people across cultures): self-direction, universalism, benevolence, conformity, tradition, security, power, achievement, hedonism, stimulation" (Sagiv & Schwartz, 2000: 178-179).
<i>Life orientation</i>	According to Scheier, Carver & Bridges (1994: 1065), life orientation refers to "individual differences in generalized expectancies for positive versus negative outcomes".
<i>Social desirability</i>	The evaluation of a respondent's tendency to give socially desirable responses (see e.g. Hays, Hayashi & Stewart, 1989). This is considered as a critical aspect that should be taken under consideration in the current study.
<i>Life satisfaction</i>	Among other aspects of subjective well-being, the <i>Satisfaction With Life Scale</i> (which is used in the current study) is narrowly focused to assess global life satisfaction. Diener and his colleagues (e.g. Diener et al., 1985; Pavrot & Diener, 1993) suggest a measurement that is based on the overall judgment of life people make according to their own criteria. Life satisfaction it is considered as a cognitive judgemental process.
<i>Locus of control</i>	Sapp and Harrod (1993) have adjusted the Levenson's locus of control scale (1974). In this conceptualization locus of control is viewed as a construct measured by three scales. In particular, according to Levenson (1973: 1-2) "... on the <i>Internal, Powerful Others, and Chance</i> scales a personal-ideological distinction has been made. All the statements are phrased so as to pertain only to the S himself. They measure the degree to which an individual feels he has control over what happens to him, not what he feels is the case for "people in general" ... The rationale behind differentiating two types of externals stemmed from the reasoning that people who believe the world is unordered would behave and think differently from people who believe the world is ordered but that powerful others are in control. In the latter case a potential for control exists".

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
<i>Emotional Intelligence</i>	Rahim et al. (2002) proposed a scale to measure emotional intelligence based on Goleman's theory. The basic axis of this model are described as following: " <i>self-awareness</i> (the ability to be aware of which emotions, moods, and impulses one is experiencing and why), <i>self regulation</i> (the ability to keep one's own emotions and impulses in check, to remain calm in potentially volatile situations, and to maintain composure irrespective of one's emotions), <i>motivation</i> (the ability to remain focused on goals despite setbacks, to operate from hope of success rather than fear of failure, delaying gratification, and to accept change to attain goals), <i>empathy</i> (one's ability to understand the feelings transmitted through verbal and nonverbal messages, to provide emotional support to people when needed, and to understand the links between others' emotions and behavior), <i>social skills</i> (one's ability to deal with problems without demeaning those who work with him or her, to not allow own or others' negative feelings to inhibit collaboration, and to handle affective conflict with tact and diplomacy)" (Rahim et al., 2002: 305).
<i>Mindfulness</i>	Mindfulness "... is generally defined to include focusing one's attention in a nonjudgmental or accepting way on the experience occurring in the present moment... It can be contrasted with states of mind in which attention is focused elsewhere, including preoccupation with memories, fantasies, plans, or worries, and behaving automatically without awareness of one's actions...In this approach mindfulness is a set of skills that includes: observing, describing, acting with awareness, accepting (allowing) without judgement" (Baer, Smith & Allen, 2004: 191; Höfling et al., 2011)
<i>Conflict management strategies</i>	Four styles of handling interpersonal conflicts have been proposed: integrating, obliging, dominating, and avoiding .These styles have been measured using Rahim's Organizational Conflict Inventory, which is used to construct the two dimensions as follows: a) Problem solving strategy = Integrating style - Avoiding style, and b) Bargaining strategy = Dominating style - Obliging style (Rahim, 1983; Rahim et al., 2002).

<i>Construct</i>	Definition
<i>Assertiveness</i>	According to Lin et al. (2004: 657), "assertiveness is a core interpersonal behavior, important to interpersonal communication. An assertiveness training program is designed to improve an individual's assertive beliefs and behaviors, which can help the individual change how they view themselves and establish self-confidence and interpersonal communication". A well-known instrument of assertiveness, and widely used is the Rathus Assertiveness Schedule. "The RAS instrument can be used both in research that investigates the efficacies of various procedures for shaping assertive behavior and for obtaining pre- and post-measures of assertiveness... how people would behave in specific situations in which assertive, outgoing behavior can be used with profit" (Rathus, 1973: 406).

This project exploits both qualitative and quantitative research methodologies in order to holistically approach its research objectives and investigate in depth the latent aspects of WLB, as well as the critical factors formulating the relationship between work and personal/family life. Thus, this project's findings are the product of a synthesis of an extended field survey based on a structured questionnaire (paper and pencil and web questionnaire), a focus group analysis and a series of interviews.

3.1. Structured questionnaire design (quantitative research)

Building on the aforementioned literature review and the selected factors (antecedents and consequences) determining WFB, a pilot survey was carried out, in order to ensure the validity of the scales adopted, to adapt them in the Greek reality and develop a more parsimonious final instrument by eliminating factors that were found to contribute less to the phenomena under investigation. This exercise yields the final structured questionnaire which is consisted of the following variables, as indicated in table 5 and depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Conceptual framework for the field research (quantitative research)

Table 5. Questionnaire design (scales)

Scale	Definition	Variable type
Work-family balance	The “accomplishment of role-related expectations that are negotiated and shared between an individual and his/her role-related partners in the work and family domains” (Grzywacz & Carlson, 2007: 458)	Personal
<i>Antecedents</i>		
Work/family negative/positive spillover	Spillover refers to the bidirectional effects between work and family (i.e., work-to-family, family-to-work) that generate similarities between the two roles (Edwards & Rothbard, 2000). [...] positive (i.e., experiences from one domain facilitate performance in another domain) as well as negative (i.e., experiences from one domain inhibit the fulfillment of demands in another domain) spillover (Allen, 2012)” (Cho et al., 2013: 188)	Work/Family
Creative Efficacy	Self- “An individual’s set of beliefs that she or he is able to solve problems requiring creative thinking and to function creatively, is becoming an increasingly popular area of research” (Karwowski, 2012: 3)	Personal
Emotional intelligence	“A set of interrelated skills concerning “the ability to perceive accurately, appraise, and express emotion; the ability to access and/or generate feelings when they facilitate thought; the ability to understand emotion and emotional knowledge; and the ability to regulate emotions to promote emotional and intellectual growth” (Mayer & Salovey, 1997: 10).	Personal
Dispositional optimism	(Life Orientation Test – Revised, LOT-R). “Individual differences in generalized outcome expectancies” (Scheier & Carver, 1985, cited in Williams, 1992: 475)	Personal
Work Engagement	“A positive, fulfilling, work-related state of mind that is characterized by vigor, dedication, and absorption” (Schaufeli et al., 2002: 74)	Personal
Work-home segmentation preferences	“The degree to which the individual prefers a workplace that helps segment work and home domains” (Kreiner, 2006: 492-493)	Personal
Work recovery experiences	Strategies individuals use to “...unwind and recuperate from work during leisure time...” (Sonnentag & Fritz,	Personal

Scale	Definition	Variable type
	2007: 204)	
Coping strategies (Coping Strategy Indicator Scale)	"Coping responses that people bring to bear on life's problems." (Amirkhan, 1990: 1066)	Personal
Spouse support	"The amount of instrumental aid, emotional concern, and informational and/or appraisal functions from a spouse" (Michel et al., 2011 cited in Helmlé, Botero, & Seibold, 2014: 116).	Family
Work culture - Supportive supervision	The degree to which an individual's "supervisor understands their family demands" (Clark, 2001: 353)	Organizational
Work Demands	The "perceived amount of work in terms of pace and volume" (Spector & Jex, 1998: 358)	Work/ Organizational
Psychological job control	"The degree to which an individual perceives that s/he can control where, when, and how s/he works" (Kossek et al., 2006: 350)	Work/ Organizational
Job insecurity	"...an overall concern about the continued existence of the job in the future" (Van Vuuren, 1990: 16-19; Hartley et al., 1991, cited in De Witte, 1999: 156)	Work/ Organizational
Perceived organizational support	"Employees... general beliefs concerning how much the organization values their contributions and care about their well-being" (Rhoades, Eisenberger & Armeli, 2001: 825)	Work/ Organizational
Leader-member exchange (LMX)	"...the characteristics of the working relationship as opposed to a personal or friendship relationship, and this trust, respect, and mutual obligation refer specifically to the individuals' assessments of each other in terms of their professional capabilities and behaviours" (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995: 237-238)	Work/ Organizational
Team-member exchange (TMX)	"...team members' perceptions of the reciprocal exchange relationship existed between themselves and team members" (Seers Petty & Cashman, 1995)	Work/ Organizational
Workplace anxiety	"Feelings of nervousness and apprehension about the accomplishment of job tasks" (McCarthy, Trougakos, & Cheng, 2015: [2])	Work/ Organizational

Scale	Definition	Variable type
Work Stress	"...the subjective evaluation of the level of experienced stress associated with specific stressors", namely "challenge stressors were defined as work-related demands or circumstances that, although potentially stressful, have associated potential gains for individuals; hindrance stressors were defined as work-related demands or circumstances that tend to constrain or interfere with an individual's work achievement and that do not tend to be associated with potential gains for the individual." (Cavanaugh et al., 2000: 65)	Work/ Organizational
Occupation role reward value	The degree to which an individual's "...occupational role is an important means of self-definition and/or personal satisfaction" (Amatea et al., 1986: 832)	Work/ Organizational
Consequences		
In-role performance	"Behavior required by formal job descriptions" (Riketta, 2002: 258)	Work/ Organizational
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Organizational (OCB-O)	"Prosocial behavior that [is] intended to benefit the organization" (McNeely & Meglino, 1994: 839)	Work/ Organizational
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Interpersonal (OCB-I)	"Prosocial behavior that [is] intended to benefit specific individuals" (McNeely & Meglino, 1994: 839)	Work/ Organizational
Job satisfaction	"The degree of satisfaction with the work itself, degree of satisfaction with coworkers, degree of satisfaction with supervision, degree of satisfaction with promotional opportunities, and degree of satisfaction with pay" (Price & Mueller, 1986, cited in Wright & Cropanzano, 1998: 488).	Personal
Career satisfaction	"The satisfaction individuals derive from intrinsic and extrinsic aspects of their career, including pay, advancement, and developmental opportunities (Greenhaus, Parasuraman & Wormley, 1990, cited in Judge et al., 1994: 4).	Personal
Quality of life (World Health Organisation)	"Individuals' perceptions of their position in life in the context of the culture and value systems in which they live and in relation to their goals, expectations,	Personal

Scale	Definition	Variable type
quality of life- Abbreviated Version WHOQOL-BREF)	standards and concerns” (World Health Organization, 1996: 5)	
Emotional exhaustion (Maslach Burnout Inventory)	“Feelings of being overextended and depleted of one’s emotional and physical resources” (Maslach, Schaufeli & Leiter 2001: 399)	Personal
demographic variables		
Core demographic variables	Gender, age, ethnicity	Personal
Time balance/ Free-time activities/ Household chore hours	Hours dedicated to work, household chores and family care, personal time and sleep in a typical day (24 hours)	Work/ Organizational / Personal/ Family
Family structure/ characteristics	Marital status, number & age of children, care provision for: disabled child/adult, elderly person, unemployed family member, spouse partner job status	Family
Salary status	Monthly net income	n/a
Overheads	Rent expenses	n/a
Job/ career status	Position in the hierarchy (top management, middle management, clerical)	Work/ Organizational
Work schedule/ flexibility	Flexible work arrangements, shift-work/ night shifts, 6-day work/ working on bank holidays	Work/ Organizational
Sector/ Industry	Public/ Private sector	Work/ Organizational
Department	Administration, accounting, sales, Warehousing/ inventory, production	Work/ Organizational
Economic hardship	The degree to which the economic crisis has caused the individuals economic hardship.	Personal

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Control variable: Social desirability: The degree to which respondents tend to distort their responses either from “...an unconscious tendency to provide inflated, positive self-reports” or “...due to intentional faking” (Ellingson et al., 1999: 156).

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
ΠΑΙΔΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΘΡΗΣΚΕΥΜΑΤΩΝ
ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

All scales used to measure antecedents, consequences and WFB (table 5) have been proposed in the relevant literature and empirically validated by several scholars (e.g. Amatea et al., 1986; Amirkhan, 1990; Anderson et al., 2001; Anderson, Coffey & Byerly, 2002; Burnett et al. (2010));

Caplan et al., 1975; Carlson et al. 2009; Cavanaugh et al., 2000; Cho et al., 2013; Clark, 2001; Cropley et al., 2012; De Witte, 2000; Einsenberger et al., 1997; Emslie & Hunt, 2009; Gander et al. (2010); Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995; Greenhaus, Collins & Shaw, 2003; Greenhaus et al., 1989; Helmle et al. 2014; Hill 2005; Hill et al., 2004; Ivancevich & Matteson, 1983; Karasek et al., 1998; Kreiner, 2006; Maslach & Jackson, 1981; McCarthy & Goffin, 2004; McCarthy et al., 2015; Parasuraman et al., 1992; Richman et al., 2008; Roskies & Louis-Guerin, 1990; Ryff et al. 2007; Sandman, 1992; Satpathy, Patnaik, & Jena, 2014; Schaubroeck et al., 1994; Schaufeli & Bakker, 2003; Scheizer, Carver & Bridges, 1994; Seers et al., 1995; Seierstad & Kirton (2015); Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007; Spector & Jex, 1998; Tiernay & Farmer, 2002; Tomer et al., 2015; Trougakos et al., 2008; Turnley et al., 2003; Vander Elst et al., 2014; Williams & Anderson, 1991; Wong & Law, 2002; World Health Organization, 1996; Wright & Cropanzano, 1998).

3.2. Interview design

A detailed interview guided was developed (both in English and Greek) in order to support the interviewer in meeting the research objectives of this study, in alignment with the research design and conceptual framework discussed. The interview was audio-taped, and lasted about an hour. Participants' anonymity was protected, as we chose a pseudonym for each participant that is used for the analysis of the interview data. During the interview, a three page questionnaire with graphical scales was delivered and filled in. An indicative time schedule and the topics discussed are presented in table 6.

Table 6. Indicative time schedule, semi-structured questionnaire topics.

	Time (min)	Total (min)	Semi-structured questionnaire (topics)	3-pages Questionnaire (in the beginning of each stage)
1	3-5	5	Present Status - Biographical data -	<u>Starting:</u> 1 st page Demographics
2	8-10	15	Everyday life- routine - Orientation/ locus of control- quality of life	<u>Starting:</u> 2 nd page Family- Personal life
3	(3-5)	(18)	*Coping with change	
4	8-10	30	Life satisfaction - recovery/recreational/ free time activities	
5	8-10	38	Family satisfaction	
6	8-10	48	Job satisfaction	<u>Starting:</u> 3 rd page (workplace questions)
7	10-15	60	**Work-life balance experiences, negative spillover, stress, coping strategy	<u>Starting:</u> 3 rd page (work-life balance)

* optional. ** At least 15 minutes

3.3. Focus group research design

Based on the literature review, we outline the process of conducting the qualitative research via focus groups, by utilizing the Nominal Group Technique (NGT) for the investigation of work-life balance of women employees.

The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) was adopted for focus groups analysis, as it is designed to promote effective group participation in the decision-making process. The Nominal Group Technique can be conducted by small groups (e.g. up to 8 participants) in order to reach consensus on the identification of key problems or in the development of solutions.

In this project, an adaptation of the NaviGaTor v3.0 toolkit in order to fit to project's objectives was used to facilitate focus group implementation and analysis. The NaviGaTor v3.0 toolkit was developed and adapted by KEK ELTA S.A. (Hellenic Post's Vocational Training Center) researchers providing a structured and systematic participative methodology to support complex group decision-making (Marentakis et al., 2016).

The Nominal Group Technique originally coined by Delbecq and Van de Ven (1971), is a structured weighted-ranking method for group decision-making that helps prioritize organizational issues and decisions after a series of idea-generation, brainstorming and voting steps aiming at reaching consensus.

This approach supports group consensus, especially when individuals with diverse roles and backgrounds are involved in constructing a logic model and the list of outputs for a specific decision is too long and therefore has to be prioritized. In this case the central question to consider would be: "which of the ideas listed for a decision are most important to achieve our goal and are easier to implement and measure?".

In the NGT, decision-makers (participants) are brought together in a focus group led by a facilitator. First, the facilitator presents the topic to the participants. During this phase, participants have the opportunity to ask questions or briefly discuss the scope of the topic. Then, they are asked to think about and write down their ideas anonymously and at the end the facilitator collects anonymous responses and announces them to the participants.

who are then asked, discussed and elaborate on them. During this brainstorming session the facilitator edits the responses (merge, rephrase, delete etc.) based on the discussion and formulates a final list of ideas - responses. Finally, each participant votes secretly on the ideas considered to be most important/effective for the given decision topic.

The main benefits of NGT are as follows:

- It prevents the domination of the discussion by a single participant (bias elimination)
- It encourages all group members to get involved and gets input from all
- Generates a greater number of ideas compared to traditional unstructured group discussions
- Depending on members' profiles, it leads to the generation of a diverse set of ideas
- Results in a set of prioritized solutions / decisions providing a sense of closure
- Diminishes competition and pressure to conform
- It is very time efficient, since each step of the process evolves in a given time frame
- It achieves group's consensus
- It enriches participants' in depth knowledge regarding the decision-making process

A short guide for the facilitator of the focus groups was developed, as facilitator's role is crucial for the successful implementation of the focus groups and the quality of its outcome. The facilitator should create a warm and friendly atmosphere, be focused and a good listener. She/he should provide direction and keep the flow of the process and be knowledgeable about the topic. The facilitator must be skilled at drawing information and opinions from participants, keeping the group focused, encouraging participation, preventing conflicts, asking for clarification and teasing out detailed information. She/he must remain neutral and should not influence the discussion while challenging, probing and exploring each decision topic. The assistant facilitator (where needed) takes notes carefully, monitors the process and manages the logistics of the process.

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During an almost three hour session of each focus group, the NGT was adopted four times (sessions), investigating

- (a) the factors (causes/antecedents) affecting the relationship between work and personal/family life.
- (b) the effects (consequences) of the relationship between work and personal/family life.
- (c) the ways participants adopt to manage the relationship between work and personal/family life (coping strategies/ work recovery activities).
- (d) the ways (policies, practices, initiatives etc) that the external environment (organizational, industrial, national level) affects the relationship between work and personal/family life.

Each focus group participant was able to suggest 10 ideas maximum at the beginning of each session, and the NaviGaTor toolkit returned the 5 more important ideas, based on the votes placed by the participants at the end of each session. When the four sessions were completed, the top 5 ideas for each one session were presented on the screen for further elaboration. Finally, participants as a group had to design paths linking causes, effects, work recovery activities and external interventions of WLB, based on causality.

3.4. Questionnaire design for research intervention measurement

Based on the training curriculum orientations, a baseline and a follow up measurement instrument of the training intervention were developed. The measurement instrument was designed according to the axes of the training curriculum for the intervention. These three axes were:

- a) Self representation,
- b) Construction of a self-development plan, and
- c) Management of relationships and negotiation skills.

The first axis represents participants' *self-representation* during the intervention's sessions and issues regarding self-perception, personal values, and motivation were explored.

The second axis refers to the construction of a *self-development* plan, and issues regarding time organization and management, goal setting, action planning and activities management were discussed.

Finally, the third axis which dealt with individual's relationship with others, under the topic of *relationships and negotiations*, reflects on the dialogic self, assertiveness, conflict styles and management, patterns and types of communication, and negotiation techniques.

In particular, based on the extended literature review regarding WLB dimensions, its dimensions, its antecedents and its consequences (literature review, section 1 of this report), a structured questionnaire was developed to measure the above aspects and thus to evaluate training intervention's outcomes.

However, marginal differences were detected among participants' perceptions before and after the research intervention, apart from stimulating awareness of WLB issues & adopting coping strategies, given the limited number of observations and duration of the program.

4. Sampling criteria

4.1. Six core clusters of sampling criteria

Based on the literature review (see e.g. Casper et al. 2007; Chang, McDonald & Burton 2010), we outline the preliminary sampling criteria for the recruitment of the participants in both the qualitative (focus groups, interviews) and the quantitative (field survey via structured questionnaires) research investigating work-life balance of women employees.

Six basic axes and sub-axes for selecting the sample are proposed, among which there are interconnections, synergies and conflicts at all levels, as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2. The conceptual framework of the different characteristic levels of impact

*1) Age and career stage: Employees from different age groups is also very important to be included in the qualitative research design. The split of age groups could be based on or aligned with the different phases of an employee's career development. For example, we could select participants at:

- a) Entry-level (e.g. less than 25 years old),
- b) Early career stage (e.g. 26-35 years old),
- c) Middle career stage (e.g. 36-45 years old),
- d) Mature career stage (e.g. 46-55 years old), and
- e) Pre-retirement career stage (e.g. over 55 years old).

*2) Occupational category: A number of broad categories have been proposed in the relevant literature (Police/ Military forces, Health associate professionals, Academics/Teaching associate professionals, Hospitality professional, Engineers, Social servants, Lawyers/ judges, legislators, senior officials and managers, professionals, technicians and associate professionals, Clerks); however, in order to group them into smaller and more meaningful categories for the purposes of this research, we suggest the following categorization according to data on gender representation in occupational categories:

- a) predominantly "female" occupations,
- b) predominantly "male" occupations, and
- c) relatively gender balanced occupations.

An analysis of occupational data from the European Social Survey round 5 (ESS, 2010), reveals some indicative occupations in each of the three categories (Table 7).

Table 7. Share of females and males in selected occupational categories (based on ISCO-88)

Raw data source: ESS (2010). N=45788 employees from BE, BG, SZ, CY, CZ, DE, DK, EE, ES, FR, FI, UK, GR, HR, HU, IE, IL, LT, NL, NO, PO, PT, RU, SE, SI, SK, UA

*3) Type of employment: Work conditions in the public sector are usually highly regulated by law as compared to the private sector. In contrast to private sector employees and freelancers, individuals working in the public sector are usually more protected, and work in 'sheltered' posts. Therefore, it is essential for the study to incorporate members of all three groups (i.e. public, private, and self-employed).

Particular attention should be paid to flexible work conditions, as flexibility on time and location of work has been argued to positively influence work life balance. On the other hand, if we view flexibility in terms of a precarious job condition in the context and as a result of the economic crisis, it is very important to explore how part time employees or shift workers, for example, perceive their work life balance.

4) Job stressors: Workload, high and conflicting work demands, lack of job autonomy and control are some of the most frequently cited causes of job stress. Potential stressful conditions have been found to have implications for work life balance. In order to define some meaningful categories regarding this sampling criterion, we could use Karasek's job demand-control (D-C) model. According to this model, stress arises when job demands are high and job control is low. So, in the formation of the sample we could use the four categories identified by Karasek: passive work (low job demands, low job control), senseless work (low job demands, high job control), active work (high job demands, high job control), and straining work (high demands, low control).

In this axis, we could also take into consideration that some occupations have been found to be correlated with high stress levels and burnout, such as employees in health care, in education, in customer service etc.

*5) Marital and parental status: Marital and parental status is also an important factor in work-life balance. The implications to work life balance are different for single employees, for employees that are in a relationship, and for employees that are in a relationship with one or more children.

The level of employer support for responsibilities and activities performed by the employees outside the work environment can diminish work-family conflict that is experienced by employees. If there is such a consideration by the employers, employees not only feel more committed to their workplace, but it is less likely that they feel their life is out of balance. Reasonably, this stands for all employees regardless of their individual background and personal circumstances, as work-life balance matters to all employees. Maybe employees in a relationship with one or more children are facing more difficulty in finding a balance between their different roles, but it is very interesting to explore and illustrate different aspect of the phenomenon under consideration interviewing participants with different marital/parental status.

In particular, it is important to include individuals who are members of a single parent family. Reasonably enough, one of the most consistent family characteristics predicting

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imbalance between work and life is being a parent. This factor is expected to affect single parents more strongly. Therefore, is crucial to include them in the sample. It would be also interesting to explore potential differences between this family status and others that also have some special interest such as traditional single-earner parents, and dual career parents.

6) "Disadvantaged groups": We believe there are some social groups that demand extra attention in this study. For example, it is crucial to include in the sample some participants from *other cultural backgrounds*. Participants from a different cultural background may experience work-life balance or conflict differently. The different perceptions and attitudes these employees may have towards work, family, and work-family pressures, the different experiences they have and the difficulties occurred during their effort to adjust, and to be included in the society and workforce.

On the top of those, we suggest to approach participants from one more category (7) "Union/Organisation/state expert": An agent for example familiar with the legal framework, the public policies, the organizational initiatives supporting work-life balance in a particular workplace or the monitoring of the application of these policies, will provide critical input to qualitative research (focus groups). This group may include representatives from the General Confederation of Workers of Greece (GSEE), from the Civil Servants Supreme Administrative Council (ADEDY), the Directorate of Labor Inspection, the General Secretariat for Gender Equality etc.

It is also crucial to include the view of other key stakeholders, such as business owners (e.g. the Federation of Greek Industries), entrepreneurs, top executives, and HR managers.

4.2. Sampling guidelines for current research

Interview process

It was recommended that interviewees should fulfill at least three of the aforementioned criteria, such as three criteria marked with an asterisk*.

Focus Groups

The three scheduled focus groups should meet the aforementioned criteria, while at the same time each one may have an overall orientation such as health care/public domain, private sector, or self-employed participants, with the latter two having an expert in public & organizational policies for WLB.

Quantitative field research

Given that a total number of 600 women employees have been set as a research objective, the sampling frame of the quantitative research should aim at employees occupied in the following domains:

- a) Public sector
 - a. Health care
 - b. public administration/organizations such as municipalities, central government etc
 - c. education (secondary and higher education)
- b) Private sector (employees of corporations, SMEs, and self-employed)

It should be mentioned that women employees represent a small proportion of the total workforce. In Greece, the employment rate for women was 48.9% in 2009 and 41.1% in 2014, the lowest in EU-28, while employment rate for men was 73% in 2009 and 58% in 2014 (Eurostat, 8/2015²). Moreover, previous empirical studies highlight that it is also very

² [http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Employment_rates_for_selected_population_groups,_2004%E2%80%932014_\(%25\)_YB16.png](http://ec.europa.eu/eurostat/statistics-explained/index.php/File:Employment_rates_for_selected_population_groups,_2004%E2%80%932014_(%25)_YB16.png)

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difficult to reach self-employed participants, especially in Greece suffering from a harsh economic crisis.

Thus, the sampling frame should be flexible in order to achieve the research objective of 600 female employee participants, and also it is interesting for the research framework to allow the comparison of the WLB level realized by female and male counterparts.

5. Field research Sample Profile (quantitative)

5.1. Basic Demographic Characteristics

The aim of the study was to assess the level of Work-Life Balance (WLB)³ among female employees, working in various organizations, both private and public, in the Attica prefecture of Greece. For the collection of primary data a structured questionnaire was developed, which was organized into two core sections: the demographic variables section and the core scales section. All scales used to measure questionnaire constructs were adopted by previous studies. The selected items were translated in Greek. Then the back translation method was utilized to ensure that all items accurately reflect the content of the original scales. All items are measured using a 7-point Likert-type scale. The questionnaire was delivered both by surveys at the workplace (printed format), as well as through internet (web questionnaire). No statistical significant differences were detected for the variables under investigation between the early and late respondents, as well as the questionnaire form (printed, web-based).

Following the sampling plan, participants were employees from the private sector (large corporations and SMEs), teachers (secondary education), lecturers (higher education), nurses and doctors working in hospitals, and civil servants/government officers (public administration, government/ministry department, and municipality). The final sample of the extended survey comprises 654 women, from different sectors (see Figure 3); participants' age ranged from 16 to 65 years of age (mean: 42.7; std. 9.1). With respect to family status, the vast majority of respondents are married (see Figure 4), while 70% has one or more children; Children's age range from infants to adults (mean: 1.9 years old, SD: 1.7). Concerning their educational level, 40% of the research participants have a Bachelor's

³ In this report, the terms *Work-life Balance* and *Work-Family Balance* are used interchangeably considering the sample of women employees; following theoretical argumentation presented at the literature review and questionnaire design sections.

degree and 17% holds a Master's degree (see Figure 5). Moreover, 277 men filled in the questionnaire in order to enrich information needed for multiple correspondence analysis and participants profiling (total sample of 931 participants).

Figure 3. Sector respondents' distribution

Family Status

Figure 4. Family Status

Education

Figure 5. Education

Figure 6. Work Experience

Figure 7. Level of Hierarchy

Participants were also asked to indicate their work experience and their position within the organization (level of hierarchy). The majority of respondents belongs in the 11-20 years tenure group (Figure 6), while 38% of the participants are front-line employees (Figure 7).

5.2. Typical Day Hour Distribution

Research participants were asked to describe how they allocate their time on a typical day, among work, family care/ household chores (FHC), personal/ leisure time (PT) and sleep. On average, respondents indicated spending 8.4 hours per day at work, 5.4 hours for taking care of their families and home and 6.8 hours for sleeping. Their personal or leisure time amounts to 3.1 hours per day (see also Figure 8).

Figure 8. Typical Day Hour Distribution

Correlation analysis among daily activities (Table 8) indicated a rather strong negative correlation between time spend on family/ household care and personal time ($r=0.619$, $p<0.01$) and a rather low negative correlation between the former and sleep ($r=0.374$, $p<0.01$). This finding suggests that the time dedicated to household and family chores is at the expense of respondents' personal time as well as the hours they sleep. Work time has also a mediocre statistically significant negative correlation with sleep hours ($r=0.241$, $p<0.01$). Results of the correlation analysis are also schematically presented in Figure 9.

Table 8. Typical Day Hour Distribution: Correlation Analysis

<i>Typical Day Hour Distribution: Correlation Analysis</i>				
		Work	Family/House Care	Personal Time
Family/House Care	r	-0.281**		
	p	0.000		
Personal Time	r	-0.253**	-0.619**	
	p	0.000	0.000	
Sleep	r	-0.241**	-0.374**	0.081*
	p	0.000	0.000	0.044

** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

Figure 9. Typical Day Hour Distribution (Correlogram) ⁴

⁴ Positive correlations are depicted in blue and negative ones in red colour. Colour intensity and the size of the circle are relative to the correlation coefficients.

6. Data Analysis

For the purpose of statistical analysis of the primary data collected, descriptive statistics were used to assess sample's characteristics. Principal Component Analysis (PCA- Exploratory Factor Analysis) was conducted and Cronbach's coefficient alpha was calculated to confirm the internal reliability of each scale.

Correlation analysis, both parametric and non-parametric depending on the variables examined, was also employed, to test for possible associations among variables under investigation. The conceptual models developed were analyzed using multivariate statistical analysis, via Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). In order to further explore the relationship between work life balance and positive-negative spillover, a multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) was conducted, developing participants' profiles in the full sample of both males and females.

6.1. Scale reliability - Exploratory Factor Analysis

Principal Component Analysis (PCA- Exploratory Factor Analysis) was conducted to identify latent factors within the constructs under investigation. Factors with eigenvalues greater than one were extracted from the data, based on the Kaizer criterion. These principal components accounted for over 70% of the total variation. For the multidimensional constructs (i.e. Work/family positive/negative spillover, Coping strategies, Work recovery activities and Quality of life), we decided to apply a normalized varimax rotation, as this is the most standard computational method of rotation to bring about simple structure. A cut-off of 0.50 was used for item scale selection. Following an inspection of the items' loadings on each factor, the distinct principal components were corresponded to the dimensions expected, and they are presented in Table 9.

Thus, four factors were extracted for the construct Work/family positive/negative spillover (*WFPS: Work-family positive spillover, WFNS: Work-family negative spillover, FWPS: Family-Work positive spillover, FWNS: Family-Work negative spillover*), three factors for Coping

strategies (*Problem solving, Seek support, Avoidance*), seven for Work recovery experiences (*Psychological detachment, Relaxation, Mastery, Control, Rumination, Work activities, Social Interactions*), and six for Quality of life (World Health Organisation quality of life- Abbreviated Version - WHOQOL-BREF). (*Physical health, Psychological Health, Social Relationships, Environment*).

Preceding PCA, the Bartlett sphericity testing on the degree of correlation between the variables ($p < 0.001$) and the Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) index verified the appropriateness of the sample. Cronbach's coefficient alpha was calculated to test for the internal reliability of each scale, as recommended by Flynn et al (1990), ranging approximately from 0.56 to 0.94. Thus, all sub-scales exhibited well over the minimum acceptable reliability level of 0.7, apart from OCB0, and relaxation. Each one of these scales consists of two items. Table 2 presents descriptive statistics, and reliability analysis indices of all scales.

Table 9. Descriptive Statistics and Reliability Analysis coefficients

Scale	Mean	S.D	Cronbach's alpha
Work-family balance (WFB)	5.19	0.987	0.902
<i>Antecedents</i>			
Work/family negative spillover	3.83	1.420	0.823
Work/family positive spillover	3.69	1.354	0.777
Family/Work negative spillover	2.95	1.325	0.784
Family/Work positive spillover	4.44	1.281	0.708
Creative Self-Efficacy	5.05	1.108	0.847
Dispositional optimism	4.42	1.401	0.894
Dispositional pessimism	3.58	1.290	0.709
Work Engagement	4.24	1.276	0.919
Work-home segmentation preferences	5.75	1.287	0.893
Spouse support	5.11	1.191	0.908
Work culture - Supportive supervision	4.77	1.536	0.938
Perceived organizational support	3.83	1.420	0.918
Work Demands	4.64	1.343	0.872
Psychological job control	4.08	1.512	0.874
Job insecurity	3.06	1.349	0.816
Leader-member exchange (LMX)	4.80	1.344	0.927

Scale	Mean	S.D	Cronbach's alpha
Team-member exchange (TMX)	4.71	0.949	0.878
Workplace anxiety	2.88	1.452	0.942
Work Stress	3.53	1.592	0.784
Occupation role reward value	4.13	1.395	0.823
<i>Coping strategies</i>			
Problem solving	5.06	1.121	0.871
Seek support	4.88	1.356	0.908
Avoidance	2.98	1.373	0.794
<i>Work recovery experiences</i>			
Psychological detachment	4.26	1.486	0.872
Relaxation	4.04	1.373	0.560
Mastery	4.40	1.478	0.900
Control	4.70	1.390	0.818
Rumination	3.74	1.331	0.840
Work activities	3.16	1.557	0.901
Social Interactions	4.52	1.399	0.856
<i>Consequences</i>			
In-role performance	5.79	1.044	0.929
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Organizational (OCB-O)	5.45	1.227	0.671
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Interpersonal (OCB-I)	5.16	1.085	0.772
Job satisfaction	3.97	1.136	0.826
Career satisfaction	4.15	1.314	0.869
Emotional exhaustion	3.16	1.666	0.868
<i>Quality of life (World Health Organisation quality of life- Abbreviated Version - WHOQOL-BREF)</i>	4.26	0.806	
Physical health	4.65	1.118	0.858
Psychological Health	5.03	0.998	0.722
Social Relationships	5.13	1.109	0.752
<i>Environment</i>	5.01	1.022	0.788
<i>demographic variables</i>			
Economic hardship	5.26	1.442	0.869

** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

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6.2. Descriptive statistics

In Figures 10 & 11, mean scores of all variables, i.e. WFB antecedents and consequences are exhibited.

Considering WFB antecedents, work-home segmentation scores at the highest level, followed by creative self-efficacy, spouse support, and problem solving as a coping strategy.

Regarding WFB consequences, in role performance showed the highest mean score followed by OCB-O (Organizational Citizenship Behaviour - Organisation).

Figure 10. Mean scores (7-point Likert scale) of WFB antecedents.

Figure 11. Mean scores (7-point Likert scale) of WFB consequences.

In Figures 12 & 13, mean scores of all variables, i.e. WFB antecedents and consequences are displayed in descending order.

Figure 12.

Mean scores (7-point Likert scale) of WFB antecedents in discerning order.

Figure 13. Mean scores (7-point Likert) of WfB consequences in discerning order.

6.3. Correlation Analysis

Pearson correlation analysis was conducted to test the relationships between the variables under investigation. Table 10 illustrates the bi-variate Pearson correlations between Work-Family Balance (WFB) and the variables describing the antecedents and consequences of WLB.

Table 10. Pearson correlation coefficients

Scale	WFB (women sample) Pearson correlation	Sig.
Work-family balance (WFB)	-	-
Antecedents		
Work/family negative spillover	-0.082*	0.036
Work/family positive spillover	0.080*	0.042
Family/Work negative spillover	-0.107**	0.006
Family/Work positive spillover	0.183**	0.000
Creative Self-Efficacy	0.496**	0.000
Dispositional optimism	0.193**	0.000
Dispositional pessimism	-0.109**	0.006
Work Engagement	0.312**	0.000
Work-home segmentation preferences	0.224**	0.000
Spouse support	0.323**	0.000
Work culture - Supportive supervision	0.253**	0.000
Perceived organizational support	0.188**	0.000
Work Demands	0.103**	0.009
Psychological job control	0.138**	0.000

Scale	WFB (women sample) Pearson correlation	Sig.
		○
Job insecurity	-0.139**	0.00 ○
Leader-member exchange (LMX)	0.165**	0.00 ○
Team-member exchange (TMX)	0.332**	0.00 ○
Workplace anxiety	-0.220**	0.00 ○
Work Stress	-0.099*	0.011
Occupation role reward value	0.162**	0.00 ○
<i>Coping strategies</i>		
Problem solving	0.374**	0.00 ○
Seek support	0.078*	0.048
Avoidance	-0.114**	0.00 4
<i>Work recovery experiences</i>		
Psychological detachment	0.179**	0.00 ○
Relaxation	0.092*	0.019
Mastery	0.200**	0.00 ○
Control	0.282**	0.00 ○
Rumination	-0.003	0.946
Work activities	-0.055	0.161
Social Interactions	0.167**	0.00 ○
<i>Consequences</i>		
In-role performance	.500**	.000
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Organizational (OCB-O)	.107**	.006
Organizational Citizenship Behavior - Interpersonal (OCB-I)	.376**	.000
Job satisfaction	.192**	.000

Scale	WFB (women sample) Pearson correlation	Sig.
Career satisfaction	.218**	.000
Emotional exhaustion	-.142**	.000
Quality of life (World Health Organisation quality of life- Abbreviated Version - WHOQOL-BREF)	.357**	.000
Physical health	.245**	.000
Psychological Health	.252**	.000
Social Relationships	.321**	.000
Environment	.318**	.000
demographic variables		
Economic hardship	.073	.064

** Significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * Significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results reveal that all correlations are significantly related to WFB at least at the 5% significance level, apart from Rumination, Work activities (work recovery activities), and economic hardship. Thus, the central and important role of WFB in the conceptual framework proposed at the personal and organizational context was confirmed.

In particular, in-role performance ($r=0.500$, $p<0.001$) is the most dominant consequence of WFB, followed by OCB-I ($r=0.376$, $p<0.001$), and quality of life ($r=0.357$, $p<0.001$). All quality of life dimensions are strongly related to WFB, highlighting its strong impact. Regarding WFB antecedents, creative self-efficacy ($r=0.496$, $p<0.001$) prevails, followed by spouse support ($r=0.323$, $p<0.001$), Team-member exchange (TMX) ($r=0.332$, $p<0.001$) and work engagement work engagement ($r=0.312$, $p<0.001$).

It is interesting that the expected negative associations of WFB with negative Work to Family ($r=-0.082$, $p<0.05$) and Family to work spillovers ($r=-0.107$, $p<0.05$), dispositional pessimism ($r=-0.109$, $p<0.01$), Job insecurity ($r=-0.139$, $p<0.001$), Workplace anxiety ($r=-0.220$, $p<0.001$), Work Stress ($r=-0.099$, $p<0.05$), avoidance ($r=-0.114$, $p<0.01$) and Emotional exhaustion ($r=-0.142$, $p<0.001$), were confirmed.

In Figures 14 & 15, Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB associations with its antecedents and consequences are exhibited.

Figure 14. Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB antecedents (with asterisk * are marked non-significant correlations).

Figure 15. Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB consequences.

In Figures 16 & 17, Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB associations with its antecedents and consequences are exhibited in descending order.

Figure 16. Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB antecedents in descending order (with asterisk * are marked non-significant correlations).

Figure 17. Pearson correlation coefficients of WFB consequences in descending order.

Thus, the expected and the resulted associations between the various variables under investigation and WFB are displayed at the following Table 11.

Table 11. Pearson correlation coefficients

Antecedents	Expected	Results	(Hypothesis)
Work/family negative spillover	-	-0.082*	supported
Work/family positive spillover	+	0.080*	supported
Family/Work negative spillover	-	-0.107**	supported
Family/Work positive spillover	+	0.183**	supported
Creative Self-Efficacy	+	0.496**	supported
Dispositional optimism	+	0.193**	supported
Dispositional pessimism	-	-0.109**	supported
Work Engagement	+	0.312**	supported
Work-home segmentation preferences	+	0.224**	supported
Spouse support	+	0.323**	supported
Work culture - Supportive supervision	+	0.253**	supported
Perceived organizational support	+	0.188**	supported
Work Demands	-	0.103**	Supported (+)
Psychological job control	+	0.138**	supported
Job insecurity	-	-0.139**	supported
Leader-member exchange (LMX)	+	0.165**	supported
Team-member exchange (TMX)	+	0.332**	supported
Workplace anxiety	-	-	supported
		0.220**	
Work Stress	-	-0.099*	supported
Occupation role reward value	+	0.162**	supported
Coping strategies			
Problem solving	+	0.374**	supported
Seek support	+	0.078*	supported
Avoidance	-	-0.114**	supported
Work recovery experiences			
Psychological detachment	+	0.179**	supported
Relaxation	+	0.092*	supported
Mastery	+	0.200**	supported
Control	+	0.282**	supported
Rumination	-	-0.003	Not supported
Work activities	-	-0.055	Not supported
Social Interactions	+	0.167**	supported
Consequences			

In-role performance		+	0.500**	supported
Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB-O)		-	0.107**	supported
Organizational Interpersonal (OCB-I)		-	0.376**	supported
Job satisfaction		+	0.192**	supported
Career satisfaction		+	0.218**	supported
Emotional exhaustion		-	-0.142**	supported
Quality of life		+	0.357**	supported
Physical health		+	0.245**	supported
Psychological Health		+	0.252**	supported
Social Relationships		+	0.321**	supported
Environment		+	0.318**	supported
demographic variables				
Economic hardship		-	0.073	Not supported

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed). * at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

It is worth noting that all expected associations (hypotheses) were confirmed (supported), apart from two out of seven work recovery activities (i.e. Rumination, Work activities) which they failed to be related significantly to WFB.

In addition, work demands proved to facilitate WFB, although a reverse relationship was expected. This positive association may be partially attributed to the financial crisis in Greece, and the vulnerability of the Greek labour market. Greek debt crisis lead to high unemployment rates (Greece suffers with the highest unemployment rate in EU, that is 23%, Eurostat, 2017), and deregulation of the Greek labor market. In this derailed labor market, one in five workers (22.48%) are employed part-time or on job rotation (flexible work forms), and only half (42.6%) of employees work full time, while one in two on flexible work contracts earn less than €500 per month (ERGANI Information System/ERGANI Center for Employment, 2017). In this dramatic situation of employment in Greece, job positions with higher demands may be considered as a reassuring factor increasing job security and commitment of the individual to the employing organization.

6.4. Introduction to Structural Equation Modeling (SEM)

The theoretical models developed were analyzed using multivariate statistical analysis, via Structural Equation Modeling (SEM). Bagozzi and Yi (1989, p. 282) argue that SEM has the following advantages over other (traditional) statistical analysis methodologies:

1. *More general procedures which overcome the restrictive assumption of homogeneity in variances and covariances of the dependent variables across groups...*
2. *Provide ways to correct for measurement error in the measures of variables ...*
3. *Facilitate a more complete modeling of theoretical relations, beyond the confinement of associations among measures.*
4. *Covariates can be treated as latent variables, thereby permitting a correction for attenuation and increasing the chances that valid experimental effects will be detected.*
5. *Constitute flexible, convenient procedures, easily implemented.*

The testing of hypotheses in the research model is performed through path analysis, which “involves the estimation of presumed causal relations among observed variables” (Kline, 2005, p. 93). This kind of analysis helps the estimation of both direct and indirect effects, as well as total effects, of the independent (or exogenous) constructs on the dependent (or endogenous) construct(s). Indirect or mediator effects “involve one or more intervening variables presumed to “transmit” some of the causal effects of prior variables into subsequent variables” (Kline, 2005, p. 98).

6.5. Spillover Effects (SEM)

To test the effect of the four spillover constructs on work/life balance (WLB), as well as the impact of the later on its three most commonly referenced outcome variables, namely Job Satisfaction, In-role Performance and Quality of Life, path analysis was performed. The results are schematically represented in Figure 18. Fit indices indicated that the model fitted the data well (see Figure 18). Overall, the structural model explains 5% of the variance in WLB, 28% of the variance in quality of life, 27% of in-role performance and 18% of the variance in job satisfaction.

With respect to the impact of work on personal life (spillover), neither construct was found to pose a statistically significant direct effect on work/life balance. However, both negative and positive “personal life to work spillover” variables are indicated by the analysis as directly affecting WLB ($\beta = -0.13$ & $\beta = 0.20$, $p < 0.001$, respectively). This finding suggests that the achievement of balance between an individual’s personal and work life depends on how the personal life influences ones work life but not vice versa.

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As for outcome variables, statistically significant direct effects of WLB on job (in-role) performance ($\beta = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$), quality of life ($\beta = 0.25$, $p < 0.001$) and job satisfaction ($\beta = 0.15$, $p < 0.001$), were indicated by the analysis. These findings provide support for the focal role the achievement of balance between personal and work life plays on a person’s assessment of quality of life, job satisfaction, and first and foremost on how well she performs on the job.

Analysis also indicated that WLB does not fully mediate the effects of spillover on the outcomes included in the model. In more detail, work to life negative spillover was found to negatively influence job satisfaction perceptions ($\beta = -0.26$, $p < 0.001$), while work to life positive spillover has a positive influence ($\beta = 0.30$, $p < 0.001$). These results indicate that a person’s evaluation of her job depends, at least partially, on how it affects her personal life.

As regards personal life to work spillover variables, they were indicated by the analysis to pose statistically significant influence on job performance and quality of life. In more detail,

personal life to work negative spillover was found to negatively affect both job performance and quality of life ($\beta = -0.08$, $p < 0.05$ & $\beta = -0.13$, $p < 0.001$, respectively), while positive spillover effects of personal to work life have a positive influence on quality of life perceptions ($\beta = 0.18$, $p < 0.001$). These findings suggest that the pressure an individual feels when her personal or family life interferes with her job can harm her job performance and degrade her quality of life, as opposed to when personal life enriches ones work life.

Finally, as regards the associations among the three outcome variables of the model, job satisfaction was found to have a noteworthy positive effect on quality of life ($\beta = 0.29$, $p < 0.001$), suggesting that satisfaction with her job is pivotal to a high quality of life. In turn, quality of life was found to positively influence in-role performance ($\beta = 0.12$, $p < 0.001$), indicating that a how well one performs at her job is also affected by her general well-being.

Figure 18. Structural Model 1: Spillover (WL/LW P/N/ spillover) Variables, WLB and consequences

6.6. Work/Life Balance and Personality Variables (SEM)

To assess the impact of personality variables on work/life balance achievement, two separate structural models were tested. Structural Model 2 (Figures 19.1 & 19.2) includes the “work recovery experiences” and the Structural Model 3 (Figure 20) the “coping strategies” multi-dimensional constructs as WLB antecedents. Both models include the four dimensions of the “quality of life” hyper-construct, namely *physical and psychological health, social relationships and environment*. In both cases, indices indicated that the model fitted the data well (see Figures 19.1, 19.2 & 20). As for their explanatory power, Structural Model 3 and 4, explain 11% and 15% of the variance in WLB, 14% and 6% of the variance in physical health, 17% and 9% of the variance in physiological health, 23% and 13% of the variance in social relationships, and 15% and 11% of the variance in environment dimensions of quality of life, respectively.

6.7. Work Recovery Experiences (SEM)

Work recovery experiences refer to activities people individuals engage in to “...unwind and recuperate from work during leisure time...” (Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007: 204). These activities include a) social interactions; b) control, i.e. “the degree to which a person can decide which activity to pursue during leisure time, as well as when and how to pursue this activity” (Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007: 207); c) psychological detachment, i.e. a sense of being away from work (Etzion, Eden, & Lapidot, 1998); d) relaxation; e) mastery experiences, i.e. “off-job activities that distract from the job by providing challenging experiences and learning opportunities in other domains” (Sonnentag & Fritz, 2007: 206); f) affective and problem-solving rumination, i.e. the emotional experience of being unable to distance oneself from job related thoughts and thinking about work related issues (Cropley et al., 2012); and g) work activities, i.e. the engagement with unfinished work at home.

Of the seven strategies people employ to recuperate from work during their leisure time, five were indicated by the analysis to pose statistically significant impact on WLB (see Figure 19.1).

More specifically, control ($\beta=0.24$, $p<0.001$), mastery ($\beta=0.13$, $p<0.01$) and psychological detachment ($\beta=0.12$, $p<0.01$), positively affect WLB, while engaging in work activities at home has a weak but statistically significant influence on WLB ($\beta=-0.07$, $p<0.1$).

Interestingly, relaxation was also found to negatively affect WLB ($\beta=-0.11$, $p<0.05$). This finding may be, at least partially explained, by the guilt women, especially mothers, feel in their attempt to fulfill their socially prescribed roles. As Douglas and Michaels (2004) explain, one of the three essential features of a good mother - as required by the "good mother ideology", what they call "the new momism" - is having to psychologically, physically, intellectually and emotionally dedicate themselves to their children. In other words, "good mothers" "...are expected to approach motherhood joyfully and completely, while sacrificing themselves to the demands of motherhood" (Sutherland, 2010: 314). In that sense, taking time for oneself comes in conflict with women's socially acceptable behavior, which demands putting others first. As Guendouzi (2006: 907) points out "society still expects that mothers should be with their children for lengthy periods of time and that spending quality time with their families on weekends is a prerequisite to good family dynamics."

As regards outcomes, WLB was found to affect all four "quality of life" dimensions, which were also found to be directly affected by several of the work recovery strategies included in the model (see Figure 19.2). In more detail, social interactions have a statistically significant positive impact on social relationships ($\beta=0.30$, $p<0.001$), on the environment facet of the quality of life construct ($\beta=0.24$, $p<0.001$), as well as an equally strong effect on physical and psychological health ($\beta=0.19$, $p<0.001$). This finding denotes the centrality of social support for the participants' physical and psychological well-being.

Moreover, relaxation was found to have a statistically significant positive impact on the "physical health" and "environment" dimensions of the quality of life construct ($\beta=0.15$ & $\beta=0.09$, $p<0.01$, respectively). At the same time, mastery has a positive effect on psychological health ($\beta=0.18$, $p<0.01$) and social relationships ($\beta=0.11$, $p<0.01$). Finally, engaging in work activities at home has a weak but statistically significant effect on physical

health ($\beta=0.07$, $p<0.1$), while rumination negatively impacts the “environment” dimension of quality of life ($\beta=0.06$, $p<0.1$).

Overall, the results regarding work recovery experiences suggest that at least some of them are fairly aiding to achieving balance between personal/family and work lives. More importantly, they can be beneficial (or harmful) to ones quality of life. As previously noted, engaging in social interactions, as a means to recuperate from work, seems to be particularly benign to participants’ quality of life perceptions.

Figure 19.1. Structural Model 2: Work Recovery Experiences (mediated effects)

Figure 19.2. Structural Model 2: Work Recovery Experiences (non-mediated effects)

6.8. Coping Strategies (SEM)

Coping strategies refers to “coping responses that people bring to bear on life’s problems” (Amirkhan, 1990: 1066), comprising three dimensions: problem solving, i.e. “direct instrumental responses” to the problem situation, avoidance, i.e. “the purposeful attempts at withdrawal or distraction” and seeking support, i.e. “efforts to contact others for comfort or advice” (Amirkhan, 1990: 1070).

Analysis indicated (see Figure 20) that two of the three coping strategies in the model have a statistically significant effect on WLB. In particular, the problem-solving strategy has a positive direct impact on the achievement of balance ($\beta=0.37$, $p<0.001$), while the avoidance strategy a negative direct impact ($\beta=0.11$, $p<0.01$). Conversely, the “seeking support” dimension does not pose any statistically significant impact on WLB. These results suggest that the achievement of balance between personal and work life can be achieved when people actively seek to solve everyday problems, while passive responses can have a detrimental effect of WLB.

However, “seeking support” and avoidance were indicated by the analysis to directly impact quality of life. More specifically, the first was found to be positively associated with “social relationships” ($\beta=0.15$, $p<0.001$) and “environment” ($\beta=0.08$, $p<0.01$) dimensions of the “quality of life construct”. On the other hand, avoidance negatively affects both psychological health and social relationships ($\beta=-0.16$ & $\beta=-0.11$, $p<0.01$, respectively).

Finally, regarding WLB outcomes, analysis replicated the positive influence on all four quality of life dimension, as was the case with Structural Model 2 (see Figure 20).

Figure 20. Structural Model 3: Coping Strategies

6.9. Work-Life Balance and Work-related Variables (SEM)

The effect of several work-related variables on WLB was also examined (see Figure 21). In more detail, the influence of job demands, job stress, workplace anxiety and support, by both individuals' immediate supervisor, as well as the employing organization was tested.

As regards WLB outcomes, job satisfaction, in-role performance and quality of life constructs were included in the model, as was the case with Structural Model 1 (see Figure 18). With respect to model fit, fit indices indicated a good fit of the model to the research data, while

this model has the strongest explanatory power of the four models tested in this study; the exogenous variables collectively explain 15%, 28%, 33% and 28% of the variance in WLB, quality of life, job satisfaction and in-role performance, respectively.

Results regarding WLB antecedents indicated that job demands, contrary to expectations, have a positive influence on the achievement of balance ($\beta=0.17$, $p<0.001$). Job demands also have a positive direct effect on in-role performance ($\beta=0.08$, $p<0.05$). These results can be explained under the lens of the Lazarus and Folkman's (1984) "two-dimensional work stressor framework", according to which job stressors, such as high job demands, heavy workload and job complexity are perceived by individuals as challenges, contrary to such things as role ambiguity or conflict, that are generally viewed as hindrances. This is because, amongst other reasons, being able to cope with a highly demanding job gives, at least to some individuals, a strong sense of personal accomplishment (Fernet, Guay & Senécal, 2004; LePine, Podsakoff & LePine, 2005). Meta-analytical research has shown that challenge stressors not only positively influence job performance, but also have the ability to offset the negative impact of hindrance stressors on the behavior (LePine, Podsakoff & LePine, 2005). Alternatively, this positive association may have its roots on the financial crisis in Greece, and the resulting vulnerability in the Greek labor market, where high job demands may act as a reassuring factor increasing job security and commitment between the organization and the well-qualified individual (see Correlation Analysis, Section 5).

Of the two stress-related variables, only workplace anxiety was found to have a statistically significant impact on WLB ($\beta=-0.25$, $p<0.001$). Nonetheless, job stress has a negative direct effect on quality of life ($\beta=-0.09$, $p<0.05$), while workplace anxiety was found to negatively influence participants' in-role performance ($\beta=-0.11$, $p<0.01$) and quality of life assessments ($\beta=-0.09$, $p<0.05$).

On the other hand, support variables included in the model, i.e. immediate supervisor support and organizational support culture, have a positive direct effect on WLB ($\beta=0.21$ & $\beta=0.14$, $p<0.001$, respectively). Additionally, both support variables have noteworthy positive effect on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.46$, $p<0.001$, for supportive organizational culture

and $\beta=0.20$, $p<0.001$, supervisor support), while support from the organization also positively influences in-role performance ($\beta=0.14$, $p<0.001$).

Finally, with respect to WLB outcomes, results fully replicate the findings of Structural Model 1 (see Figure 18). More specifically, WLB has a positive influence on in-role performance ($\beta=0.42$, $p<0.001$) and quality of life ($\beta=0.24$, $p<0.001$) and a weak positive influence on job satisfaction ($\beta=0.06$, $p<0.1$). Job satisfaction was again found to directly affect respondents' assessment of their quality of life ($\beta=0.28$, $p<0.001$), which in turn positively impacts in-role performance ($\beta=0.13$, $p<0.001$).

Figure 21. Structural Model 4: Work Variables

6.10. Concluding Remarks of the SEM Analysis

Participants of this research comprise women employed both in the public and private sectors, of which the majority is married and has at least one child. Respondents reported a fairly high level of balance between their personal and work lives (mean score: 5.2, SD: 1.0) and a rather stable work schedule. As Tausig and Fenwick (2001) argue, schedule regularity allows individuals to effectively plan their time and differentiate more clearly between their work and family time, contributing in higher levels of perceived WLB.

Correlation analysis among time segments of a typical day revealed that time devoted to household chores is primarily at the expense of respondents' personal time, followed by sleep hours. Relevant research has indicated disparities between genders, taking marital status into consideration. This may be because mothers give priority to house and family care over leisure, as prescribed by the cultural expectations of their role as care givers (Milkie & Peltola, 1999), which in turns allows family members to regard mothers' time as a "collective, household resource" (Passias, Sayer, & Pepin, 2016: 5).

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As regards WLB outcomes, the current study has to show for some noteworthy findings. More specifically, research results indicated that the achievement of balance between women's personal/family life and work life plays a major role in their job performance, while it also affects their feelings towards their job. These findings highlight the centrality of WLB on both affective and behavioural outcomes at work. Moreover, WLB positively influences participants' assessment of their quality of life, both in general, as well as in terms of its various facets. In more detail, the achievement of balance between family and work life is advantageous for one's social relationships, her psychological and physical health, as well as the perceptions of the quality of their living conditions.

Except for WLB, interface between work and personal life was indicated by the results to have independent effects on the outcomes examined. Regarding work outcomes, the negative (positive) spillover of work to family life diminishes (increases) individuals' job

satisfaction, while family to work negative spillover harms job performance. Also, the positive interface of family to work life improves quality of life.

All the aforementioned findings stress the importance of establishing policies aiming to improve women's work/life balance and the positive interface between an employee's work and non-work life, both at the Government and company/organizational levels. This need is further maintained considering the beneficial effects of support, individuals feel they receive at work, coming from both their supervisors and the organization as a whole, not only on their perceptions of balance achievement, but also on job and quality of life satisfaction.

With respect to the impact of work on personal life, neither construct was found to pose a statistically significant direct effect on work/life balance. However, both negative and positive "personal life to work spillover" variables are indicated by the analysis as directly affecting WLB. These results suggest that the achievement of balance between women's personal and work life depends on how the former influences the latter but not vice versa. This finding mirrors the prioritization of the motherhood and care taker role of women, over that of an employee (Noor, 2004), that is largely dictated by established societal roles of men and women, by which "...a father is the primary earner and mothers the primary carer" (Burnett et al, 2010: 563) Results of the analysis of the qualitative data from the current study also support this finding, as women participants report primarily identifying with their mother and caregiver role (see *Qualitative Research Findings- WLB of women employees project, Section 8*).

The study also focused on two personality-based factors - i.e. work recovery experiences and coping strategies - that are largely "trainable traits", so as to assess their impact on WLB. As previously noted, recovery experience comprise a set of activities that individuals employ to relax and recuperate from work, during their non-work hours. Of the seven activities included in the study, being able to choose in which activity to engage (*control*), learning new or doing challenging things (*mastery experiences*) and mental and physical disengagement from work (*psychological detachment*) were found to positively influence women's sense of balance. *Relaxation, mastery and social interactions*, are also positively

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
ΠΑΙΔΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΘΡΗΣΚΕΥΜΑΤΩΝ
ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

associated with participants' perceptions of quality of life. Conversely, engaging in *work activities* at home and *rumination* are negatively associated with WLB and physical health, respectively. Prior research on training interventions for work-family conflict reduction has also indicated that such techniques as mental blocking or engaging in some kind of activity, e.g. exercise, play music, meeting with friends, can enhance positive mood and mind-states and relieve from stress, preventing work from negatively impacting life at home (Molineux, Fraser & Carr, 2013; Kreiner, Hollensbe & Sheep, 2009).

The importance placed on social relationships by the women in study is further highlighted by the positive influence *support seeking*, as a coping mechanism, has on their assessment of quality of life. The weight women place on *supportive environments*, in their homes (spouse support) and at work (supervisor and organizational support), is also indicated by the study findings (see also *Correlation Analysis in Section 5 of this Report*). Balance between work and family life also increases by taking action (problem solving) over avoiding dealing with difficulties.

All the above suggest that policy makers should focus on establishing schemes in the form of formal arrangements and programs, that will be able to actively communicate and provide practical and psychological support to individuals in their effort to effectively balance their parental and work roles. These schemes can take various forms from flexible work arrangements to special training programs; the latter can assist employees in coping with the pressures coming from both facets of their daily lives, by establishing positive affective and behavioral responses to stress factors. As it is evident from the findings of this study, such initiatives can be proven beneficial to both employees and employing organizations, as work/life balance is major contributing factor to improved quality of life, job satisfaction and performance.

7. The Relationship between WLB and Spillover in Different Population Groups

7.1. Multiple Correspondence Analysis

In order to further explore the relationship between work life balance and positive-negative spillover, a multiple correspondence analysis (MCA) was conducted, using the software R and, in particular, the FactoMineR package (Lê, Jossz, & Husson, 2008). In this analysis were exploited the full sample of both males and females, comprising a sample of 931 participants.

The following main variables were used in the multiple correspondence analysis:

- WLNS: WORK-LIFE NEGATIVE SPILLOVER
- WLPS: WORK-LIFE POSITIVE SPILLOVER
- LWNS: LIFE-WORK NEGATIVE SPILLOVER
- LWPS: LIFE-WORK POSITIVE SPILLOVER
- WLB: WORK-LIFE BALANCE

Initially, the above variables were measured using a 7-point scale. For the current analysis, every variable was re-coded into three categories. As it is presented in the bulleted list above, the recoding was based on the frequency distribution of each variable to form as equal groups as possible. Thus, for each variable:

- In the first group are included those respondents who had the relatively lower values, and in particular those who disagreed with the meaning expressed in each variable (they disagreed e.g. that there is a negative spillover of their work life into their personal life or that they experience work life balance in their lives).

- The second group comprises those who had relatively medium scores in the respective variables, in other words, those with a neutral stance toward what was expressed by the conceptual content of each variable (e.g. they believed that they experience neither balance nor imbalance between their work and personal life).
- The third group consists of those who agreed with the meaning expressed in each variable (they agreed e.g. that there is a positive spillover of their personal life into their work life or they believe that they have a work life balance in their lives).

The variable LWPS was divided in two groups, since above the 60% of participants had scored the value 4 or 5. In this case, the first group represented those who had relatively lower LWPS and the second those who had relatively high (see Table 12).

Table 12: Frequencies and percentages of the main variables (N=931)

Variables	Categories	Frequencies	Percentages
Work life negative spillover	Low	372	40
	Medium	278	29.9
	High	281	30.2
Work life positive spillover	Low	406	43.6
	Medium	270	29
	High	255	27.4
Life work negative spillover	Low	354	38
	Medium	270	29
	High	307	33
Life work positive spillover	Low	480	51.6
	High	451	48.4
Work life balance	Low	226	24.3
	Medium	364	39.1
	High	341	36.6

The demographic variables that were used in this analysis and their categories are presented in the following list (frequencies are presented in Table 13):

- gender: male, female
- age: 30, 31-40, 41-50, 51 and above.
- education: compulsory, upper secondary, post-secondary, graduate studies and postgraduate studies/PhD.
- marital status: single, divorced/widowed, married, in a long-termed relationship
- children: no children, only one child below 18, one child below 18 and other adult children, two or more children below 18, adult children
- provide care to: nobody, aged, adult/child with disabilities, , unemployed member of the family
- net monthly income: up to 800€, up to 1200€, up to 1600€, 1600€ and above
- employment sector: education (includes all levels), health, rest of the public sector, private sector,
- years of employment: up to 1 year, 2-4 years, 5-9 years, 10-19 years, 20 years and above
- employment status: full time, part time, unlimited time contract, limited time contract, work contract
- hierarchical level: front-line employee, front-line management, middle management, top management
- working hours: office time, night shift, bank holidays-weekends, flexible work hours (depends on employee), flexible work hours (depends on employer)

Table 13. Frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables (N=931)

Variables	Categories	Frequencies	Valid Percentages
Gender	Female	650	71
	Male	265	29
Age	<31	101	11.8
	31-40	264	30.7
	>50	165	19.2
	41-50	329	38.3
Education	Basic	73	8
	Upper secondary	177	19.4
	Post-secondary	118	12.9
	Graduate studies	363	39.7
	Postgraduate studies	183	20
Sector	Education	73	7.8
	Health	346	37.2
	Private	113	12.1
	Public	399	42.9
Work experience	<1y	30	3.3
	1-4y	79	8.7
	5-9y	144	15.9
	10-20y	344	37.9
	20+	310	34.2
Employment status	Contract	25	2.9
	Fixed Work	92	10.5
	Full Time	430	49.1
	Part Time	29	3.3
	Unlimited	300	34.2
Level of hierarchy	Level_Bottom	325	39.8
	Level_Low	203	24.8
	Level_Middle	233	28.5
	Level_Top	56	6.9
Work shifts	Office hours	536	64.9
	Flexible (depends on employee)	40	4.8
	Flexible (depends on employer)	123	14.9
	Shift_Holidays	52	6.3
	Shift_Night	75	9.1
Marital status	Divorced/Widowed	86	9.6
	In Relationship	47	5.2
	Married	544	60.5
	Single	222	24.7

Table 13. Frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables (N=931) (cont)

Variables	Categories	Frequencies	Valid Percentages
Kids situation	More than 1 under 18yo	215	23.1
	1 under 18yo		
	1 under 18yo Others Adult	51	5.5
	Adult Kids	131	14.1
	None		
Provide care	Care to elder	185	19.9
	no Care	631	67.8
	Care to special needs	34	3.7
	Care to unemployed	81	8.7
Income	Income 800€ -1200€	417	47.7
	Income 1200€-1600€	165	18.9
	Income less than 800€	215	24.6
	Income over 1600€	77	8.8

The main variables (see the first list) were used in the analysis as *actives*, they contributed in the formation of the axes, whereas the demographic variables (see the second list) were used as *supplementary*, in order to help in the interpretation of the results.

7.2. Results of Multiple Correspondence Analysis

Based on the results of MCA, we adopt a 4-dimensions model which interprets the 55.2% of the total distribution of the categories of the active variables that were used in the analysis (see Table 14).

Table 14. Eigenvalue and % of distribution interpreted by each dimension of the MCA model adopted

Dimension	Eigenvalue	% of distribution
1	0.3	16.1
2	0.3	15.4
3	0.2	12.3
4	0.2	11.4
Total: 55.2%		

In the following table (Table 15), the active variables with the values of their v test for each of the dimensions in the model are presented (e.g. see Lebart, Morineau, Piron, 1997). The categories marked in the table (a different shade was used for every pole of each color, see below in the description of the profiles) are those with the largest contribution in the formation of the axes. All of them (colored) are statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 15: V test of the active variables in the 4 dimensions of the model adopted

Variables	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3	Axis 4
WLNS_1	-20.14	-7.65	5.45	-1.39
WLNS_2	8.81	7.83	13.19	10.58
WLNS_3	12.71	0.36	-18.96	-9.06
WLPS_1	-15.02	11.03	-10.22	-9.02
WLPS_2	10.84	6.69	5.66	18.18
WLPS_3	5.68	-	5.61	-8.47
LWNS_1	-19.41	-5.86	-9.57	7.57
LWNS_2	0.39	-1.04	22.25	-9.18
LWNS_3	19.66	7.05	-11.60	1.05
LWPS_1	-12.89	19.70	0.52	-1.95
LWPS_2	12.89	-	-0.52	1.95
WLB_1	1.42	18.95	3.50	-1.71
WLB_2	5.11	-2.97	2.92	-16.65
WLB_3	-6.43	13.85	-6.07	18.38

For the interpretation of each dimension, it was taken under consideration the categories with the higher v test value in each pole (positive and negative) of the dimension. These categories were also the ones with the highest contribution in the formation of the axe under consideration.

In particular, the first dimension seems to reflect the involvement or not of one sphere (work or life) to the other and the profiles emerged are the following:

- The non-involvement profile (in the negative pole of the axis, marked in *yellow* color in table 15), where there is balance between work and personal/family life. In this profile, work to life and life to work have a low negative spillover and also a low positive spillover. In other words, participants that fall into this group tend to feel that they have work-life balance, when there is neither negative nor positive spillover between work and personal/family life. In contrast, when there is no spillover between work and life, participants tend to feel that they have balance in their life.
- The involvement profile (in the positive pole of the axis, marked in *orange* color in table 15), which is characterized by medium level work-life balance, high or medium levels of work to life positive and negative spillover, it seems that when there is spillover from one sphere to the other, either negative or positive, the participants don't feel that they have high level work-life balance.

The second dimension reflects the positive or not involvement of one sphere to the other. The profiles emerged are the following:

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- the positive involvement profile (the negative pole of the axis, marked in *light blue* in table 15), where work is thought not to affect life negatively, but mainly positively, and on the other hand life is thought to affect work mainly positively, and negatively only in a low degree. This combination goes with high levels of work-life balance.
- the non-positive involvement profile (the positive pole of the axis, marked in *red* in table 15), where participants don't feel that they have work-life balance. In this case, they feel at the same time that life doesn't affect work positively, but rather negatively, and that work affects positively life in a low or medium degree, and negative in a medium degree.

It follows a graphical display (visualization) of the first two axes, where the four profiles are drawn. The profiles of the second axis are drawn with a discontinuous dash. The name of each profile falls into the respective cloud (Graph 1).

Graph 1: Profiles of the axes 1 and 2

The third dimension represents the formation of a sense for (im)balance regardless of positive or negative spillover. In particular:

- in the balance profile regardless of the negative spillover (in the negative pole of the axis, marked in *green*) it was found that participants feel that they have work life balance, although there is high negative work to life spillover, and irrespectively of the degree of work to life positive spillover or the degree of life to work negative spillover (which may be in both cases high or low).
- in the imbalance profile regardless of the positive spillover (the positive pole of the axis, marked in *rose*), it was found that life has a medium degree negative spillover to work, and work has low or medium degree of negative spillover to life and

medium or high positive spillover. Irrespectively of that, participants in this profile tend to feel low or medium work life balance.

The fourth dimension seems to reflect the negative or non-negative impact of work to the sense of balance, formulating the following two profiles:

- In the negative impact of work to the sense of balance profile (in the negative pole of the axis, marked in *light purple*) work seems to influence negatively life to a high degree and positively to a low or high degree, whereas life influences negatively work to a medium degree. In this profile, there isn't a feeling of work life balance.
- In the non-negative impact of work to the sense of balance profile (in the positive pole of the axis, marked in *purple*), work seems to influence life to a medium degree either positive or negative, whereas life seems to influence work negatively to a low degree. This combination tends to be mapped together with high levels of work life balance.

It follows a graphical display (visualization) of the last two axes. The profiles of the fourth axis are drawn with a discontinuous dash. The name of each profile falls into the respective cloud (Graph 2).

Graph 2: Profiles of the axes 3 and 4

Furthermore, in order to better understand the meaning of each axis, we displayed on them the supplementary biographical variables. In the following table (see Table 16), the v test for each supplementary variable is reported in each of the dimensions of the model. The statistically significant ($p < 0.05$) categories are colored in the table following the color schemes we used for the profiles of each axis (see above, axes description and Table 15).

Table 16: V test values of the supplementary variables in the 4 dimensions of the model adopted

Variables	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3	Axis 4
Female	1.78	-1.66	-1.03	0.13
gender.NA	-			
Male	-1.71	1.59	1.42	0.04
age_cat.NA	-1.72	0.98	0.55	-0.04
Age<31	0.14	1.62	0.78	-0.37
Age>50	0.02	-	0.35	-0.99
Age31-40	0.79	-1.62	0.84	0.01
Age41-50	0.11	1.57	-1.89	1.05
educ_rec.NA	-0.77	0.93	-0.39	-0.91
Educ1	0.97	-2.52	0.00	0.08
Educ2	-0.61	0.24	-0.11	0.79
Educ3	-	2.20	0.65	0.40
Educ4	0.03	-	-0.23	-1.34
Educ5	2.08	0.50	-0.03	0.78
Education	0.85	-2.58	0.36	-1.47
Health	1.12	1.99	-0.40	-0.27
Private	0.72	0.47	0.99	1.01
Public	-	2.03	-0.46	0.39
Exp_<1y	1.22	1.05	1.74	0.25
Exp_1-4y	0.40	1.24	0.25	-0.22
Exp_10-20y	-1.45	1.17	-0.72	1.33
Exp_20+	0.62	-1.76	0.74	-0.50
Exp_5-9y	-	-	-0.77	-0.49
work_exp_years.NA	1.13	0.09	-0.66	-1.31
Contract	-	-	0.12	-0.56
employment_status.NA	0.66	-1.96	-0.39	-0.20

1 under 18yo	0.01	-	0.06	1.53	0.52
1 under 18yo Others Adult	-1.32	0.17	0.10	-0.33	
Adult Kids	-	0.27	-1.71	-0.61	0.36
None	-2.19	1.18	-0.58	-0.68	
kids_situation.NA	0.62	0.85	1.04	-0.29	
Care to elder	1.22	0.94	-1.06	-1.25	
no Care	-	0.92	0.72	1.19	1.24
Care to special needs	0.07	-1.06	-0.30	0.61	
Care to unemployed	-	0.26	-1.81	-0.27	-0.69
income.NA	-	0.38	0.03	-1.35	-1.20
Income 800€ - 1200€	-	0.60	2.64	-1.19	2.02
Income 1200€- 1600€	-	1.04	-1.41	0.01	-0.26
Income less than 800€	-	0.67	0.28	1.77	-0.93
Income over 1600€	-1.18	-3.22	0.60	-0.81	

Regarding the first axis, in the non-involvement profile, we found mainly employees working in the *private sector* who reported *work shifts* including bank holidays and weekends. Employees falling into this profile tend also to be *men*, in a *long-term relationship* and those who have *post-secondary education*. In the other profile of this axis, the involvement profile tends to map *women*, people with *higher education*, *married* people, and people with *two or more children* less than 18 years old.

Regarding the second axis, the positive involvement profile is more common for *women*, people over *30 years* old, and mainly *over their fifties*, and people with *basic education*. Participants who tend to fall in this group work in the *education sector*, they have more than *20 years of work experience*, and they earn *up to 1200 euros or more than 1600 euros*.

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ΠΑΙΔΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΘΡΗΣΚΕΥΜΑΤΩΝ
ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

Moreover, they have *adult children*, and they have to take care for an *unemployed member* of the family. The other profile of this axis, the non-positive involvement profile, is more characteristic for *men*, people with *graduate studies*, employees working *full time* and in *night shifts*, in the *health sector*.

The balance regardless of the negative spillover profile of the third axis is more common for people who are in a *mature* stage of their career, *41-50 years old* and people who work also in *night shifts*. On the other hand, the imbalance regardless of the positive spillover profile is more characteristic for *newcomers* in the workforce.

Finally, in the fourth axis, the non-negative impact of work to the sense of balance profile is more typical for *middle management* employees, and people who earn *up to 1200 euros*.

7.3. Concluding remarks of respondents profiling

The profiles of the first axis bring out a widespread and general belief that there is no work life balance when life interferes with work and work interferes with life.

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Apart from that, in the second axis, personal life seems to play the most important role in the evaluation of interference of one sphere to the other. So, when there is a positive involvement of life to work and work to life, people tend to feel they have work life balance, and the opposite, when there isn't a positive involvement -mainly of life to work- people don't feel that they have work life balance.

The third axis denotes the autonomous function of work life balance and spillover. People tend to resist to negative spillover - mainly of work to life - and preserve their sense of balance, whereas others tend to feel an unbalanced relationship between work and life in spite of the positive spillover experienced from one to the other sphere. Thus, sometimes work life balance is built upon resilience or is projected as the main demand regardless all the positive side effects of turbulent and overwhelming personal life demands.

Finally, the last axis gives prominence to the negative impact of work to life. There is a common perception that work burdens people's lives. Indicative of this widespread

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
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ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
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perception is the etymology of the Greek word for 'work' [δουλειά, *douleia* / *doo-lia*; δουρία], which is cognate to the word 'slavery' [δουλεία, *douleia* / *doo-li'-ah*, δουρία]. The implication is that people tend to feel an unbalance, when there is a negative work to life spillover and balance when this spillover is somehow moderated. On the same line of reasoning, since work to life spillover is expected to be mainly negative, there is a sense of balance when this spillover is experienced to be at a medium level.

8. Qualitative research (main findings)

8.1. Focus group methodology (participants' perceptions)

The process of conducting the qualitative research via focus groups was designed by utilizing the Nominal Group Technique (NGT) for the investigation of work-life balance in women employees. The Nominal Group Technique (NGT) was adopted for focus groups analysis, as it is developed to promote effective group participation in the decision-making process (Delbecq and VandeVen, 1971). NGT can be conducted by small groups (e.g. up to 8 participants) in order to reach consensus on the identification of key problems or in the development of solutions.

Based on a review of the relevant WLB literature, a short structured questionnaire (metric) was developed in order to evaluate focus groups members' perceptions regarding the following variables:

Optimism, life satisfaction, family satisfaction, stress related to family and personal life, commitment to family and personal life, Spouse Support, self-efficacy related to dealing with personal life issues, Quality of Life, Job satisfaction, Job stress, Job commitment, Supportive climate, work self-efficacy, job performance, career satisfaction, impact of economic hardship, current Work life balance, ideal Work life balance.

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Three focus groups were organized at IASIS facilities, resulting to a total of 24 women employees participating in an approximately 3 hour session. The scope of the focus groups was to investigate the course of action traced through causes, effects, work recovery activities and external interventions which modify work-life balance. Adopting a systematic methodology (NGT), and using NaviGaTor 3.0. toolkit⁵ (supporting software), training needs and solutions facilitating work-life balance were identified.

⁵ The NaviGaTor v. 3.0. software toolkit coined by KEK ELTA S.A. (Hellenic Post's Vocational Training Center) researchers and aims at providing a structured and systematic participative methodology to support complex group decision-making (Marentakis, Panagos & Riga, 2016).

8.2. Statistical analysis (focus groups members' perceptions)

Performing statistical analysis of the structured questionnaires collected, the most important findings are summarized, as follows:

- There is no statistical difference for the perceptions of the focus groups members measured before and after the focus group execution for all variables under investigation except from their commitment to family and personal life. They realize that they are less committed to their family and personal life, after their completing the focus group process. The following graphs (Graphs 3, 4 & 5) illustrate focus members' evaluations before and after the focus group implementation.
- As illustrated in Graph 6, the current realization of Work life balance (WLB) is ranked with the lowest score among all variables, revealing the importance of dealing with this relationship between work and life.

Graph 3. Variables related to personal & family

Graph 4. Work related Variables

Graph 5. All variables measured by the Focus group members' questionnaire

Graph 6. All variables measured by the Focus group members' questionnaire

- Correlation analysis (Table 17) revealed that WLB is positively related to *optimism*, *life satisfaction* and negatively to *stress stemming from family and personal life*, *job stress*, *job commitment*, and *economic hardship*. It is interesting that the ideal state of WLB failed to be associated with any variable included but the current state of WLB.

Table 17: Correlation analysis (Focus groups questionnaire)

Variables	WLB (current)		WLB (ideal)	
	Correlation coefficient	Sig.	Correlation coefficient	Sig.
Optimism	0.547	0.007	0.220	0.312
life satisfaction	0.493	0.020	0.297	0.180
family satisfaction	0.343	0.110	0.341	0.111
stress related to family and personal life	-0.474	0.022	-0.291	0.178
commitment to family and personal life	0.337	0.116	0.057	0.794
Spouse Support	0.241	0.281	0.210	0.349
self-efficacy related to dealing with personal life issues	0.296	0.181	0.321	0.145
Quality of Life	0.249	0.253	0.251	0.247
Job satisfaction	0.090	0.689	-0.101	0.655
Job stress	-0.424	0.049	-0.286	0.197
Job commitment	-0.445	0.038	-0.117	0.605
Supportive climate	-0.039	0.862	-0.113	0.618
work self-efficacy	-0.080	0.723	0.163	0.470
job performance	-0.182	0.419	0.099	0.662
career satisfaction	0.365	0.095	0.101	0.654
economic hardship	-0.479	0.021	-0.327	0.128
WLB (current)			0.583	0.003

8.3. Cognitive mapping and findings of Focus groups

The scope of the focus groups was to investigate the course of action traced through causes related to WLB, as well as effects resulting from WLB, followed by work recovery activities and coping strategies, ending with external interventions which are strongly associated with WLB.

First, the causes that define the relationship between personal/family and work lives were investigated. The main reasons fueling Work-life imbalance as perceived by focus groups members were pertained to the following topics:

- Anxiety
- Crisis (and the accompanied insecurity, as well as crisis economic and political ramifications)
- Working conditions (e.g. working hours, financial rewards, working environment)
- Family issues (such as parenting, responsibilities and problems at home)

In addition, personal ambitions and overinvestment in the occupation (career orientation) were emphasized by participants, and different orientations of prioritization (quantitative to work life versus qualitative to personal/family life) were detected.

On the implications of the relationship of professional and personal/family domains in the life of the participating working women, the second question posed in each focus group, the following categories have emerged as key factors:

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- Anxiety
- Exhaustion
- Mental and physical burden of the individual

Furthermore, participants mentioned divorce as a source for conflicts, the lack of social life, and personal frustration/cancelation. It is interesting that one focus group detected positive effects of work on life, defining *occupation* as a psychological *therapy*, providing satisfaction, autonomy, and security.

The third thematic field discussed in the focus groups was related to managing the relationship between work and personal / family life. Among the coping strategies expressed, the following prevailed:

- Adaptability, flexibility
- Setting limits

- Humor, optimism
- Scheduling, planning

Moreover, two points concerning coping strategies were discussed: a) the need of women for communication with the significant ones of their life, as well as the positive effect of the social supporting network as a recovery agent, and b) the value of the work breaks. Thus, it seems that participants can recognize the difficulties and needs in the two discrete domains of personal/family life and work, however, they fail to apply the appropriate coping strategy in order to achieve balance in real life.

The last topic discussed in the focus groups was related to the external environment and specifically the ways it intervenes and modifies the relationship between work and personal/family life. The key elements of the external environment detected by the participants were the followings:

- Infringement of rights
- Taxation
- Degradation of education system
- Financial crisis and reduced earning
- A collective negativism

The latter discussion revealed the existence of a dipole expressed as "*individual vs state*", ranging from the way an individual regulates what happens in his/her life and work to the political actions the state adopts to affect citizens' personal life.

The resulting conceptual map of a focus group advancing the central role of anxiety and stress in achieving WLB, is depicted in picture 1. Similarly, another focus group developed a mental map where WLB is displayed like a wheel in constant rotation, and all around the spherical frame of reference are the causes (listed as work conditions), external factors (economic crisis and low wages), coping strategies (hobbies and social life) and emotional exhaustion as the main detrimental effect (picture 2).

Picture 1. Conceptual map of a focus group (*stress*)

Picture 2. Conceptual map of a focus group (*WLB-Sphere*)

8.4. Interview data analysis and visualization

Ten working women were interviewed, in an hour session, by trained interviewers. For a detailed presentation of the interview protocol developed, see the “Interview Guide” report of this project.

For the interview data analysis, a prototype icon-based coding system was developed, as illustrated in Diagram 1. An encoding scheme with icons was utilized in order to be able to reflect on a timeline of each participant’s standard typical day. A detailed schedule of a typical day of each participant is shown in the following diagram 1.

Diagram 1: Time schedule of a typical day for each woman interviewed

In the first column of the chart, the initials of each participant given, in the next two columns, their marital status is presented, followed by their employment statuses, whether they receive help at home, personal or work-related problems participants reported to face in their daily lives, and the overall self-assessment of their life. In pink shading are presented the working hours.

It is interesting to observe some indicative cases. For example, the participant with the initials NS (Third from the bottom) is married with a minor child, works full-time in the afternoon (as a teacher), receives help from her mother and has faced two family losses that have greatly influenced her life. In a typical day, she wakes up in the morning at 7:00, has breakfast, prepares and takes the child to school. Then she does the shopping and runs other errands and later prepares lunch and does other household chores. She goes to bring the child from school, has lunch, spends quality time with her child and then gets ready for work. On her way to work, where she commutes, she drops off her child to her mother's house; the child stays there until she gets off from work. After work, she spends some quality time with the child, then, she deals with unfinished work for a couple of hours, and at last, goes to bed at 1:00.

As regards life satisfaction, participants were asked to describe the factors that cause pleasure, factors that hinder and/or are causes for concern, and strategies applied to deal with the difficulties faced in their lives. The following categories were reported:

- Children, beautiful family moments, "thank goodness there is my family"
- Personal time, free time
- Friends, shared time with husband, relationships
- Creativity at work, employment
- Contact with nature

The factors that cause difficulties or raise concerns were the following:

- Multiple Roles
- Stress obligations-intense schedule, distance to work
- Work pressure, demanding job
- Husband's employment status-financial conditions
- Lack of understanding, co-operation in professional and personal life
- Emotional state of the individual.

The applied coping strategies reported in order to deal with difficulties, are the following, organized according to their content:

- Effort, temper kept in dealing with issues (mentioned for example in relation to the search for employment stability and this is important since in many cases, it was discussed by the participants' job insecurity issues)
- Setting priorities
- Avoidance of mistakes
- Positive Thinking
- Personal time: essential for dealing with their family role
- Peace of mind: two of the participants said that they see a therapist
- Talk with persons of confidence
- Good family life
- Fun activities into the daily routine, rehabilitation (dancing, singing with children, watching series on TV, and working-out).

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Regarding WLB, the following categories of factors proved to contribute to a more balanced relationship between work and personal/family life:

- Communication / assistance / cooperation with husband
- Help from grandparents
- Understanding from family
- Understanding from the supervisor
- Sessions with psychologist
- The personality
- Work conditions
- Calmness, patience
- Personal tranquility

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
ΠΑΙΔΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΘΡΗΣΚΕΥΜΑΤΩΝ
ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

Conversely, the following factors act as potential obstacles in the relationship between work and family life:

- Time management
- Overtime
- Conflict of roles
- Lack of time
- My own self
- The effect of the work in one's life
- Physical fatigue
- The amount of tasks
- Bringing work problems into personal/family life
- The obstacles of everyday life

8.5. Summary of Qualitative research findings

The purpose of this section is to summarize results of the in-depth qualitative investigation of various aspects of Greek working women's relationship between personal/family life and work life.

The qualitative research design involved in-depth individual interviews and focus groups. Data collection from focus groups was facilitated by the NaviGaTor v3.0 software (Marentakis, Panagos & Riga, 2016), which was adapted to the needs of this research. For the interview data analysis a prototype icon-based coding system was developed.

As the findings reveal, the daily life of women with multiple roles and obligations is characterized by limited sleep, rest and personal time, by weak social life and by minimal contacts with their spouse/partner. Their main role identity seems to remain even today this of a "mother" and a "wife". From this perspective, the qualitative and quantitative dimension of time was pointed out, the first associated with family/personal life and the second with work-life. When women spend time on themselves (quality time, but not with the family) or at work (quantitative time) they tend to feel that they neglect their family and experience remorse.

One consequence of women's family identity centrality is that work is seen as competitive and is becoming a key contributor to imbalance. Some women find that work negatively affects their lives and this belief is reinforced by the fact that at work, having family is often considered a disadvantage. Moreover, it was revealed that women develop a unified sense of self-efficacy, a general feeling of personal (in)competence. If the feeling is negative, it burdens them mentally and physically and reduces their self-esteem both when they perform at work and at home. On the other side, a general feeling of self-efficacy mobilizes women and empowers them with confidence and energy in all aspects of their lives. Furthermore, some women experience work as an opportunity for action, personal and professional development, autonomy, pleasure, security, creativity and socialization that can further provide a refuge from personal/family problems. This finding negates the beliefs of

ΥΠΟΥΡΓΕΙΟ ΠΟΛΙΤΙΣΜΟΥ,
ΠΑΙΔΕΙΑΣ ΚΑΙ ΘΡΗΣΚΕΥΜΑΤΩΝ
ΓΕΝΙΚΗ ΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΕΙΑ ΕΡΕΥΝΑΣ
ΚΑΙ ΤΕΧΝΟΛΟΓΙΑΣ
ΔΙΑΧΕΙΡΙΣΤΗΣ ΠΡΟΓΡΑΜΜΑΤΟΣ

some women about the conflictual nature of the relationship between work-personal/family lives and highlights a "therapeutic" dimension of work.

From the analysis emphatically emerged that the dynamic combination of different women's identities can be very constructive. Multiple roles may not be an obstacle but a tool to address the challenges of life. It was also highlighted the dimension of deliberate choice and personal responsibility on how women form a satisfactory relationship between personal, family and work life. The research further highlighted the need for women to constantly decide where to focus, on which side of life, and to know exactly why they made their decisions. These choices is important to be deliberate not only to help them live their lives to the fullest, but also to be able to advocate them to significant others.

It finally emerged that women are aware of a range of management strategies and tools needed to address the challenges of the multiplicity of roles in their lives. However, knowledge of appropriate strategies seems to be a necessary but not a sufficient condition to well-being and to a better quality of life.

As it emerged from this research work-life balance can be understood as a dynamic and fluid process that mutates constantly, reminding us the myth of Sisyphus. Therefore, the question seems to remain open on how to empower women to address the challenges of their various roles and to enjoy their complex daily lives as much as possible. Perhaps there is not a common answer for all women or even for each woman at different points in her life. The bet for each woman is different and has greatly to do with the meaning and value that each time she attaches to each of her roles.

8.6. Bibliography

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9. Conclusions/ Suggestions

The research conducted in the realm of the Project shed light on how working women evaluate their own experience on trying to fulfill their multiple roles, also coping with the contradictions inherent in them. Thus, it allowed us to better understand how perceptions and interpretations of social constructions (Berger P, Luckmann T, 1966) such as family life, maternity, career and work performance acquire meaning and guide the individual to live his/her life (Giddens, 1991, Mouzelis 1995). Or, in other words, it gave us insight on how mechanisms such as socialization or social construction of meaning operate today and even more important, how and in what respect cultural elements considered by various scholars (and activists!) as traditional, still exist today, and are produced and re-produced.

This aspect of the results is of more importance if placed in the greek context, where the research actually took place: there were indications that the women participants prioritize as their “main role identity [...] even today this of a “mother” and a “wife” (p.113). This finding allows us to argue that traditional elements of the greek culture are still prevailing today, thus distancing greek society from the ideals of modernity as described in literature as well as in the legal systems of EU countries. The same finding also reveals that the mechanisms that lead women to internalize the more traditional elements of their “double burden” (p.13) are still in force, thus evidencing that the dominant role model still remains the traditional one, according to which the woman’s task is primarily the family responsibilities.

Given that greek society is the context of the research, the research also revealed some of the challenges that individuals both as family members as well as employees are faced with because of the still on-going economic crisis. But, it is because of this finding that the research evidenced also constructive and rewarding strategies formed by women respondents, in their trying to handle their contradicting roles and tasks.

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The degree that the women internalize the dominant role model makes it even more crucial that measures are taken to facilitate women to achieve at least some balance between their work/personal-family life. Considering that it is women more often than men that have to invent strategies in order to comply with varying and sometimes contradicting expectations of their own and often enough of the “significant others” in their lives, also supports the same argument. This brings us to a major question of our times, already old but still up-to-date, whether the individual is left alone to cope with his/her life hardships or whether measures should be taken to support and facilitate the individual’s access to what is considered his/her right. Our premise being the latter, we nevertheless acknowledge the interaction between individual/subject and social mechanisms (Mouzelis 1995) as the motivating power of social dynamics. It is for this reason that the suggestions that follow aim at encouraging personal development while at the same time acknowledging the need for - urgent- social reforms.

In response to the challenges set by the findings of the research, we summarize in the following table our proposals on what could be done so that women could achieve a more functional and rewarding work-family and personal life balance. We focus on women because, as highlighted in other parts of this document, «[t]he goal of achieving work-life balance concerns both men and women but is achieved with more difficulty by women due to the double burden they face, which is inherent in our social role model” (p.13). Nevertheless, it is our belief that no measure or policy can actually change the existing situation without including and mobilizing the men’s commitment to it. More importantly, this “double burden” that the women have to carry and cope with, brings back? in the agenda the issue of rights: although legal recognition of equal rights is almost paramount at least in the western world, the research has revealed that the ideals of equality, emancipation and inclusion are still a challenge in the actual field of everyday life where relations take place, concepts acquire meaning and rights are enacted. It is for this reason that we strongly believe that investigating traces of inequality is also the first step towards engaging against them, in the scope of achieving a “profound transformation of the existing relations of power” (Laclau, Mouffe 2001, p. xv).

Findings	Suggestions
<p>The daily life of women with multiple roles and obligations is characterized by limited sleep, rest and personal time, by weak social life and by minimal contacts with their spouse/partner</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures that encourage fathers/ partners to participate more actively in child-caring and household chores. For example, developing parenting skills in the realm of Life Long Learning courses and activities could encourage sharing of tasks between parents and would also help towards combating stereotypes and raising awareness on women's rights. • Measures and policies to facilitate women in their everyday life and their coping with multiple tasks (childcare facilities, kindergarten places available for all) • Measures supporting single mother families • Flexible working timetable for both parents
<p>When women spend time on themselves (quality time, but not with the family) or at work (quantitative time) they tend to feel that they neglect their family and experience remorse</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Psycho-social support services and counseling should be available. The existing services should enrich their methods so that they can effectively support individual empowerment and reflective skills.
<p>Some women find that work negatively affects their lives and this belief is reinforced by the fact that at work, having family is often considered a disadvantage</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Legal action in favor of work-family balance in the workplace • Policy measures fighting gender based discrimination in workplace and employment

<p>A general feeling of self-efficacy mobilizes women and empowers them with confidence and energy in all aspects of their lives.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Life Long Learning activities and Psycho-Social Support Services focusing on developing and upgrading life- and key- skills for both men and women, such as coping strategies, problem solving etc.
<p>Research highlights a "therapeutic" dimension of work.</p> <p>Multiple roles may not be an obstacle but a tool to address the challenges of life</p> <p>The dimension of deliberate choice and personal responsibility on how women form a satisfactory relationship between personal, family and work life must be included everywhere</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures against Unemployment • Policies supporting self - development and up- grading self-efficacy • Legal actions supporting gender equality
<p>Knowledge of appropriate strategies seems to be a necessary but not a sufficient condition to well-being and to a better quality of life.</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Measures to spread these strategies through training programs and informal learning

All the organizations that took part in the Project are committed to promoting the key-concepts underlying the research, as well as to challenge well-rooted , traditional ideas embedded in the dominant social role model that affect women and their choices on unequal terms. The research has indicated that work -family balance still remains a goal for the women that took part in it, sometimes hindering them to live their life at its fullest. It is for this reason that further exploration would be valuable. Open questions that still remain have to do with how men understand and conceptualize their role as fathers and employees and even more so because their traditional role is seriously challenged in the social agenda. But, is it so also at home? Last but not at all least, further exploration of contemporary aspects of inequality, such as education level, class and social status interplay with gender and define the perception or the interpretation of the everyday experience.

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